

THE GREAT NATION 2025

Radical solutions for governance, accountability, and political reform in the Philippines

Version 1.1

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Author of The Statesman's Affidavit

Featuring more than 15 unorthodox solutions to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

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“A nation is great not by its size alone. It is the will, the cohesion, the stamina, the discipline of its people and the quality of their leaders which ensure it an honorable place in history” – Lee Kuan Yew, 1963

“Even from my sick bed, even if you are going to lower me into the grave and I feel something is going wrong, I will get up.” – Lee Kuan Yew

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CERTIFICATION AGAINST INTELLECTUAL FRAUD AND DISHONESTY

I hereby declare, upon my honor, that what I have written in this paper are the products of my own personal intellect and I have made the proper attribution of sources and references. In the event that it is established by the reader that what I have written in this paper had been obtained by me through fraudulent use of ideas or information belonging to other persons, I will acknowledge the findings and will update the citations and reference section of this paper.

The reference section in the last part of this paper is also a **work on progress**. In case some of the written ideas happen to be similar to existing ideas by other persons, I will update the reference section in the next version of this paper.

JONELLE PETER C. MUÑOZ

FULL NAME

SIGNATURE

December 9, 2024

DATE

All proposed laws, if they cannot be passed at the national level due to politics, political dynasty or a lack of majority votes, may become local ordinances applicable to any local government unit, such as a city, municipality, or province.

80% and 83%

Plato's Theory of Ideas or Forms

According to Plato “The physical world is not the real world; it is only a shadow or imitation of the true reality.”

CONFIRMATION BIAS

Confirmation bias is a cognitive bias where people have a tendency to search out, interpret, or even recall information in a way that reinforces preexisting beliefs.

According to Collins Dictionary,
“Cognitive means relating to the mental process involved in knowing, learning, and understanding things.

Examples of Confirmation Bias

Not seeking out objective facts

Interpreting information to support your existing belief

Only remembering details that uphold your belief

Ignoring information that challenges your belief

Republic of the Philippines
SANGGUNIANG PANLUNGSOD
City Government of Pasig

Ordinance No. 37
Series of 2018

AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.

Authored by: Councilor Victor Ma. Regis N. Sotto
Co-Authored by: Councilors Rodrigo B. Asilo, Ferdinand A. Avis, Regino S. Balderrama, Orlando R. Benito, Rhichie Gerard T. Brown, Mario C. Concepcion, Jr., Rosalio D. Martires, Corazon M. Raymundo, Gregorio P. Rupisan, Jr., Alejandro E. Santiago, Wilfredo F. Sityar, LIGA Pres. Rigor J. Enriquez and SK Fed. President Georgia Lynne P. Clemente

First Page of the Freedom of Information Ordinance in
Pasig City Government, 2018, *City Ordinance No. 37, s. 2018*

Section 19. Penalties. Failure of any government official or employee to comply with the provisions of this Ordinance shall be a ground for the following penalties:

1st Offense:	Reprimand;
2nd Offense:	Suspension of five (5) to thirty (30) days; and
3rd Offense:	Dismissal from the service.

Page 10 of the Freedom of Information Ordinance in
Pasig City Government, 2018, *City Ordinance No. 37, s. 2018*

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EDUCATION

Image by anonymous (n.d.)

The Thinker by Auguste Rodin (1904)
Image by CrisNYCa (2018)

NATIONAL NEWS

Resolving classroom shortage may take over 20 years – EDCOM report

By *Ashzel Hachero* 🕒 January 31, 2025

EDCOM2
The Second Congressional
Commission on Education

Image screenshot from Malaya Business Insight. Report from Congressional Commission on Education

EDUCATION

“In Indonesia, the number of schools constructed in each district from 1973 to 1975 was proportionate to the number of primary schoolchildren not enrolled in schools in 1972.” (Fernando, 2008)

“Between 1973 and 1979, more than 61,800 primary school buildings were built, making available 222 new schools and 666 new teachers per district.” (Fernando, 2008)

Proposed Law #1

A law requiring the construction of adequate primary and secondary schools in proportional to the number of out-of-school youth and adults.

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring all primary and secondary schools to be converted into extensions schools of State University and Colleges at night.

A law requiring all State University and Colleges funded by the Government to offer night classes to double school capacity.

EDUCATION

According to Guillemette (2016), most European countries offered

FREE college education like:

(1) Norway, (2) Finland, (3) Sweden

(4) Germany, (5) France, and (6) Denmark

Opportunity Cost

According to Investopedia, opportunity cost is the forgone benefit that would have been derived from an option other than the one that was chosen.

WHAT IS THE OPPORTUNITY COST OF CORRUPTION?

The Opportunity Cost of Corruption

- Lost roads, bridges, schools, and hospitals
Money stolen could have been used for public services
- Lost job opportunities
Investors avoid corrupt countries, so fewer jobs are created
- Lost trust in government
Citizens become cynical, stop cooperating, and society decays
- Lost future for the next generation
Young people inherit a broken system, harder life, and fewer opportunities
- Lost innovations and global competitiveness
Corruption blocks meritocracy; only "friends" and "relatives" succeed

Proposed Law #3

A law providing emergency student loans to poor
but highly qualified students.

Source of funds:

Local Government Funds or unused savings / budgets of some government agencies and offices.

One requirement:

A one-page letter on why the school or local government should grant the student loan.

FIGURE 3
Share of College-Age Students Enrolled in Higher Education and Attrition Rates, by Region

Note: Share of college-age population in higher education are for the year 2020 and attrition rates are for the year 2022.

Source: Bayudan-Dacuycuy et al. (2024), CPRBD (2024)

“The situation in the BARMM is particularly dire.

Its **93.4 percent dropout rate** is not just a statistic - it represents an entire generation slipping through the cracks.

Years of conflict, economic instability, and underdevelopment have made education in the region a luxury, not a right. When survival is the priority, schooling becomes an afterthought.”

- William L. Curading Jr.

Proposed Solution to Raise School Funds

Image source: BPI Website

Eight (8) Post Dated Cheques Worth P5,000 each

Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim in Mindanao

Graphic © Asia Briefing Ltd.

Proposed Law #4

A law mandating the construction of adequate six-storey school buildings in far-flung and remote areas.

'Walang Maputik, Walang Matarik,' dokumentaryo ni Kara David | I-Witness

 GMA Public Affairs ✓
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Image Screenshot from I-Witness, GMA Public Affairs

VIEWABLE
WORLDWIDE

Proposed Law #5

A law mandating the funding of adequate school buses in far-flung and remote areas.

A law mandating the funding of adequate school buses free for the poor children.

Proposed Law #6

A law providing one free nutritious meal to underweight children.

Equality vs Equity

The goal is to reduce student's drop-out rate

Proposed Law #7

A law setting the minimum hourly rate and working hours of professors
in Public State Universities and Colleges.

Minimum wage: Php 1,000 per hour

Minimum working hours per day: Three (3) hours

Minimum working hours per week: 15 hours

Minimum total salary as par time professor: Php 60,000.00 per month

Proposed Law #8

A law setting the minimum hourly rate of full-time professors
in Public State Universities and Colleges.

Minimum wage: Php 800 per hour

Minimum working hours per day: Six (6) hours

Minimum working hours per week: 30 hours

Minimum total salary as par time professor: Php 96,000.00 per month

Proposed Law #9

A law giving automatic scholarship and monthly stipend to students in a very unfortunate and special circumstances.

Source of funds:

Local Government Funds or unused savings / budgets of some government agencies and offices.

One requirement:

A one-page letter on why the school or local government should grant the student loan.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

Assess how many dropouts there were in the previous year.

The following year, the maximum number of students who can be given scholarships and stipends due to unfortunate and special circumstances can be equal to the number of dropouts in the previous year.

This can be audited by CoA at the local level to avoid possible abuse of the granting of scholarships.

There must be a record or data on the number of dropouts in every City or Municipality in a year.

Proposed Law #10

Improving Alternative Learning School (ALS) System

Allocate more budget to increase the number of ALS teachers.

There should be a minimum number of ALS teachers for every three barangays or drop-out students.

ALS teachers are a crucial workforce to help children who are forced to work due to extreme poverty.

Proposed Law #11

A Law Making the Related Learning Experience Fee (RLE) for nursing students
FREE of Charge in Public State University and Colleges

Other Option:

A school with the lowest RLE fees in the Philippines should set the maximum RLE fees for all Public State Universities and Colleges. If at least one school can minimize the RLE fees without compromising the quality of the related learning experience, then other Public State Universities and Colleges should adopt this school's best practices and itemized breakdown of RLE expenses.

Proposed Law #12

A law increasing the minimum salary of teachers in primary and secondary schools after conducting a comprehensive analysis of teachers' salaries in other Asian countries.

Option #1: P48,000 per month

Salary Options for Primary and Secondary Teachers

Option #2: The average salary of primary and secondary school teachers in Asian Countries should be the minimum salary of primary and secondary teachers in the Philippines.

Option #3: The average salary of primary and secondary school teachers in highly developed Asian countries should be the minimum salary of primary and secondary school teachers in the Philippines.

Option #4 (Ambitious but possible if there is no corruption in the Philippines): The salary of primary and secondary school teachers in Singapore should automatically be the salary of primary and secondary school teachers in the Philippines.

Proposed Law #13

A law requiring all review centers to publicize their final review materials

“The law should not discriminate between the rich and the poor.”
– common legal and philosophical principle

Other Alternative

A law banning final review or coaching after the publication of exam papers

The Professional Regulatory Commission (PRC) and the Supreme Court can issue a memorandum circular to ensure that the board exam and bar exam are fair.

The President can also issue an Executive Order (EO).

Public Policy

Improve the board and bar exam process

“The law should not discriminate between the rich and the poor.”
– common legal and philosophical principle

Recommended Board and Bar Exam Process

- Procurement of adequate printers that can print exam papers at the day of examination
- All questions shall be open and public to everyone. At least one million questions per profession.
- All board and bar questions, usually at least 300 to 400 questions, shall be randomly selected 30 minutes before the start of examination and provided that the students are already in the exam room with proctor and CCTV. No one can go out the exam room, unless there is a medical reason or other emergency reason.
- Once the 300 to 400 questions are randomly selected by a group of professionals, the questions will be emailed to all the proctors who will then print the exam papers.

Recommended Board and Bar Exam Process

The goal is to ensure that every graduate can take the board or bar exam without paying review center fees or final coaching fees.

We can improve this process or adopt some aspects of the national examination system from highly developed countries such as Singapore, Canada, or Australia.

Proposed Law #14

A law requiring all public schools to be fully air-conditioned, except in Baguio, Tagaytay, and other cold cities.

Fully air-conditioned schools can be used by Filipinos with heart-related problem and other medical conditions, as recommended by doctors and specialists.

Proposed Law #14 (High Priority)

Data Source: DOST-PAGASA
Image by Earth Shaker (2021)

Data Source: DOST-PAGASA
Image by Rappler (2021)

Proposed Law #15

A law granting full scholarships to Filipinos who pass the entrance examinations of the top 10 universities in the world, such as Harvard, Stanford, MIT, etc.

“The law should not discriminate between the rich and the poor.”
– common legal and philosophical principle

Notable Filipinos who graduated from Harvard University

- Jesse Robredo (M.P.A) – Former DILG Secretary and Naga City Mayor
- Jovito Salonga (LLM) – Former Senate President of the Philippines (1987 to 1992). He also earned his Doctor of Juridical Science (SJD) from Yale University.
- Fernando Zobel de Ayala (BS and MBA) – President (2006 to 2022) and CEO (2021 to 2022) of Ayala Corporation.
- Evelio Javier (MPA) – Former Governor of Antique (1971 to 1980)

Sample Gradual Implementation

- Stage 1 Implementation:
 - Maximum of 50 Filipinos only.
 - It can be 20 Filipinos in year 1, 20 Filipinos in year 2, and 10 Filipinos in year 3.
- Stage 2 Implementation:
 - Maximum of 100 Filipinos only
 - It can be 20 Filipinos in year 4, 20 Filipinos in year 5, and 10 Filipinos in year 6.
- Gradual increase over time based on unprogrammed national budget

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

After graduating from the top 10 schools in the world, Filipino scholar must work in government for at least five years.

Ideally, we need national and local politicians who are the best and brightest in the world. If they choose not to become politicians, they can hold top positions in the government.

Optional if they choose not to work in government:
They must return all government expenses with 20% interest.

Proposed Law #15 (Alternative)

A law **providing loans** to Filipinos who pass the entrance examinations of the top 10 universities in the world, such as Harvard, Stanford, MIT, etc.

Zero interest payable in 10 to 20 years

The government's expenses for sending Filipino scholars to top universities like Harvard, Stanford, and MIT are minimal compared to the tax revenue they generate over their lifetimes.

Proposed Law #16

A law providing government subsidies (a monthly allowance and full scholarship) to children whose mother or father died due to the war on drugs.

Practice Empathy and Compassion

Monthly allowance for K12 students and children, and full scholarship in college level.

Local government and public colleges can implement this in their localities and schools.

Video Source: Human Rights Watch (2020)

January 27, 2025

Watch the FB live of Professor Cielo Magno and Father Danny Pilaro

Very High Priority

Those children whose mother or father died because of a police officer.

COURT CONVICTS EX-COP FOR TEENAGER KILLINGS LINKED TO DUTERTE DRUG WAR

Dismissed cop Jeffrey Perez is found guilty of murdering Carl Angelo Arnaiz, 19, and Kulot de Guzman, 14, as police implemented Rodrigo Duterte's drug war in 2017

Image Source: Philippine Star (2023)

HEADLINES

Bicam boosts executive's unprogrammed funds to P531B

Jean Mangaluz - Philstar.com

December 14, 2024 | 1:03pm

All proposed laws, if they cannot be passed at the national level due to politics or a lack of majority votes, may become local ordinances applicable to any local government unit, such as a city, municipality, or province.

Proposed Law #17

A law requiring all provinces and cities with at least 250,000 population to have a PUP school

P12 per unit for undergraduate programs
or approximately P500 per semester

Proposed Law #18

A law requiring all provinces and cities with at least 250,000 population to have an affordable medical schools

P12 per unit for undergraduate programs

or approximately P500 per semester

FREE RLE Fees

Proposed Law #18

A law requiring all students who pass the
Philippine Science School entrance examination
and the DOST exam to be accepted in the program

Automatic budget from the local government
as long as the student pass the examination

BENEFITS

Regular Academic Year

- ✓ Tuition and other school fees ----- PHP 40,000 /AY
- ✓ Learning Materials and/or Connectivity Allowance ----- PHP10,000 /AY
- ✓ Monthly Living Allowance ----- PHP7,000/ month
- ✓ Clothing Allowance ----- PHP1,000 (1st Sem of 1st Year only)
- ✓ Transportation Allowance ----- 1 economy-class roundtrip fare
- ✓ Group Accident and Health Insurance ----- PREMIUM
- ✓ Thesis Allowance ----- PHP10,000
- ✓ Graduation Allowance ----- PHP1,000

Ano ang mga Benepisyo ng isang PSHS Iskolar?

- Libreng matrikula
- Libreng gamit sa mga aklat-aralin
- Buwanang baon na P4,000
- Taunang pambili ng uniporme na P1,800 (para sa maralitang mag-aaral)
- Taunang pamasaha (para sa maralitang mag-aaral)
- Libreng Pagtira sa Dormitoryo (para sa maralitang mag-aaral)

An ordinance requiring all public schools to post the benefits of DOST and Philippine Science School in their bulletin board

Proposed Law #19

A law banning all educational institution to withhold student's document

The Cudia Law

“An unfair process cannot produce a valid conviction.”

The Case of Cudia

- The PMA Honor Code required a unanimous vote (100% agreement) among the Honor Committee members to convict a cadet of an honor violation.
- Initially, the vote was 8 - 1 (not unanimous).
- After some internal pressure or discussion (based on testimonies), it appeared that the lone "not guilty" voter was pressured to change their vote - making it look unanimous.
- This manipulation violated the very foundation of the Honor System.

Source: https://lawphil.net/judjuris/juri2015/feb2015/gr_211362_2015.html

The Cudia Law

“Aldrin Jeff Cudia is innocent”.

He is supposed to graduate in the Philippine Military Academy (PMA) as the class salutatorian.

A special law can be created for a very special case.

All Bar takers in the next consecutive examination may be asked the following question:

“Based on the Supreme Court decision G.R. No. 211362, do you think Cudia is innocent?”

Answerable by yes or no, and explain why.

HEALTH

My Health My Right by Geetanjali Pathak (2024)

The Spirit of Medicine by Salomon Trismosin (1582)

Proposed Law #1

A law requiring all provinces in the Philippines to have a public tertiary hospital

Other alternatives:

Public tertiary hospital for every five (5) adjacent cities

Public tertiary hospital for all cities with more than 250,000 populations

Public tertiary hospital for all cities after filling their classroom backlogs

*five (5) and 250,000 can be changed to any integer based on unprogrammed funds in GAA

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

The public tertiary hospital shall be free of charge to all Filipinos.

Both the District Representative and the Provincial Governor must work together within three years to make this a reality.

The goal is to increase the overall lifespan of all Filipinos.

Both the rich and the poor can live longer regardless of their financial situation.

The public tertiary hospital should have free brain surgery, heart surgery, cancer treatment/surgery, and organ transplant (kidney, liver, lungs, etc...).

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring all province to have a minimum number of heart and brain surgeon based on their population

No Filipino should wait for more than 24 hours for extremely urgent cases

Amend Local Government Code of 1991 to have at least one brain and heart surgeon in Cities and Provinces with more than 250,000 population

*250,000 can be changed to any integer based on unprogrammed funds in GAA

Proposed Law #3

A law institutionalizing cancer research treatment in the Philippines

Key facts about cancer according to World Health Organization

“Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for nearly 10 million deaths in 2020, or nearly one in six deaths.”

“Around one-third of deaths from cancer are due to tobacco use, high body mass index, alcohol consumption, low fruit and vegetable intake, and lack of physical activity. In addition, air pollution is an important risk factor for lung cancer.”

“Many cancers can be cured if detected early and treated effectively.”

Reference: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/cancer>

Sample Implementation

Applicable to stage 1 cancer patients. Must have no other disease such as diabetes, kidney problem, etc...

P25,000 incentives for 30 days stay in any DOH accredited cancer facility or public tertiary hospital.

Minimum of 30 patients per study.

Free laboratory and diagnostics examinations. Required to track CA125 before the start of the study.

Free nutritious foods tailored by a licensed dietitian. No refined sugar and meat in the 30 days. Only fresh vegetables, fruits and a different variety of fish.

Incentives After Day 30

Free medicines, laboratory test, diagnostic test in the next 12 months
(as per request by cancer doctor)

Free chemotherapy and cancer surgery in a
Public Tertiary Hospital
to prevent progression to stage 2

Automatic Budget Allocation for Cancer Research per Study

A study based on the recommendation of at least three cancer specialists
or a reputable cancer organization.

We can have many studies in the future to find a cure for cancer.

We can institutionalize the process, where the three cancer specialists can submit a two-page paper about the potential of a study to at least one member of the Congress, and Congress can accept a maximum of 10 studies per year. If P250,000 can be allocated per study, then we can set a budget of P2.5 million per year. If the amount exceeds P250,000, there must be a breakdown of the cost in the one- to two-page paper.

*10 and 250,000 can be changed to any integer based on unprogrammed funds in GAA

Amendment of National Integrated Cancer Control Act (NICCA)

Republic Act No. 11215

All proposed laws, if they cannot be passed at the national level due to politics, political dynasty or a lack of majority votes, may become local ordinances applicable to any local government unit, such as a city, municipality, or province.

STRONG GOVERNMENT

Cicero Denounces Catiline in the Roman Senate by Cesare Maccari (1888)

Developed Countries	Number of Senators	Population	Population / Senator
Canada	105	40.1 Million (2023)	381,904 per senator
Australia	76	26.64 Million (2023)	350,526 per senator
United States of America	100	334.9 Million (2023)	3,349,000 per senator
Spain	266	48.37 Million (2023)	181,242 per senator
Switzerland	46	8.85 Million (2023)	192,391 per senator

Population per senator in five developed countries (2025)

Amendment to the 1987 Constitution

Increase the number of senators in proportionate to the Philippine populations

Gradual increase from 24 to 80, then to 120, and finally to 320 senators

Proposed Law #1

A law automatically increasing the number of city councilors and provincial board members in proportion to the population of their respective LGU.

Cities, municipalities, and provinces with high populations will most likely have a high number of city councilors and provincial board members.

Find the ideal population per councilor and per board member based on other highly developed countries, and then use that number as the basis for determining the ideal number of city councilors and provincial board members.

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring all legislators to publish the progress of their proposed bill with a DOI (Direct Object Identifier).

All legislators such as senators, district representatives, city councilors, and provincial board member.

Ensure that only Filipinos with bright and original minds can defend their proposed bill in the 1st, 2nd, and final reading.

Eradicate ghost writing and minimize staff expenses.

1st unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Proposed Law #3

A law requiring all **aspiring Filipino politician** to have one DOI (Direct Object Identifier) with all their published idea related to good governance and public policy.

COMELEC requirement in filing Certificate of Candidacy (COC).
Requirement to become a member of a strong political party.

The quality of a politician can be determined by the quality of his/her ideas.

1st unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

There must be a single government website with the repository of all the DOI of all aspiring and elected politicians.

We need to create a political environment in which Filipinos with brilliant ideas can thrive. DOIs can speak for themselves and their legacy.

It may improve their chance of winning an election.

Proposed Law #4

A law requiring all elective officials with veto power to document their VETO reasons and justification, along with its quantitative and qualitative analysis, on a paper with a DOI.

Veto power can be the most important and dangerous power of the President, Mayor, and Governor. It may or may not be politically motivated, and it can also be a source of great wisdom or corruption.

Use Annex section for the quantitative and qualitative analysis

It is in the public interest how politicians use their veto power.

The Philippines has a multi-trillion budget and loan every year.

This budget can be vetoed by the President if he/she has no kickback or if his/her kickback is not enough.

So, the veto power can be a source of great corruption, or it can be a source of great generosity to all Filipinos if used with great wisdom.

Proposed Law #5

A law consolidating all the bank accounts of all elective and government officials into a single bank only.

Only one bank statement of account per elected and government official.

This makes it easy to track unexplained wealth or any unexplained increase in wealth.

2nd unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

One bank statement can be used as a required attachment in the SALN (Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth). We don't need overly long attachments of debits and credits—*just one page stating the ADB or Average Daily Balance*.

This can also help the Ombudsman and the AMLC (Anti-Money Laundering Council) investigate corrupt government officials.

This kind of law is one of a kind in the whole world. I assume it will not be passed into law in the Philippines within the next three to six years unless we elect people like Leni Robredo, Heidi Mendoza, and Vico Sotto as President.

Proposed Law #6

A law limiting the maximum cash deposits of all elective and government officials in their bank accounts to only 10 million pesos.

10 million pesos can be changed to any amount just enough for retirement.

This kind of law will eradicate generational wealth of all government officials.

According to the 1987 Constitution, “All Public Officials must live a modest life.”

2nd unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

This kind of law is one of a kind in the whole world. It will never be passed into Law with the kind of Congress that we have right now.

Compromise

Only politicians elected from 2028 onwards will be covered by this law, or those who do not seek re-election or elective office will not be covered.

Other option

One consolidated bank account and a 10 million deposit limit as a requirement to become a member of a strong political party.

Proposed Law #7

A law providing a monthly pension to all elected officials who have served at least three “good terms”

Definition of “good terms”:

- No unexplained wealth, with only one bank account
- No CoA issues and disallowances
- No pending corruption cases; *they must be cleared first before receiving the monthly pension*
- Faithful submission of SALN during their terms in office

The monthly pension should be enough just to live a modest life

There would be little to no reason for corruption if we could provide a stable pension to all elected officials who serve at least three good terms.

A politician follows a unique career path. What will they do if they lose a high-stakes election? What will be their source of income?

I believe many politicians have resorted to corruption because they lack a stable source of income after their term.

Proposed Law #8

A law using a unique penalty system to all public officials

Penalty in proportion to government salary:

- First penalty: One month salary
- Second penalty for the same offence: Two months' salary
- 3rd penalty for the same offence: Ban to hold public office in the next three years

This proposed law can be improved and is open for debate

“A great man is hard on himself; a small man is hard on others.”

- *Confucious*

“Be tolerant with others and strict with yourself”

- *Marcus Aurelius*

Proposed Law #9

A law requiring all public officials to return their unexplained and generational wealth to the Republic of the Philippines, specifically for the education sector, such as building schools and purchasing school lots.

Penalty in proportion to government salary:

- First penalty: One month salary
- Second penalty for the same offence: Two months' salary
- 3rd penalty for the same offence: Ban to hold public office in the next three years

This proposed law can be improved and is open for debate

My assumption is that many politicians are reluctant to return their unexplained and generational wealth because they believe other politicians will just steal it from the government.

I once read that the unexplained wealth recovered by the Presidential Commission on Good Government (PCGG) from the Marcos family was allocated for the implementation of Agrarian Reform. My perspective is different—I believe it should have been used for the education sector such as the implementation of my Proposed Law #1: “A law requiring the construction of adequate primary and secondary schools in proportionate to the number of out-of-school youth and adults.”

Proposed Law #10

A law amending the use confidential and intelligence funds in the Government

Intelligence officers can be sourced from existing police officers, members of the army, or any retired members of the police or army. They may operate as civilians for a maximum of six months in a specific location. After six months, they shall return to their regular duties and responsibilities.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

Retired police or army personnel may also serve as intelligence officers, receiving a 5% increase in their existing salary for each month they provide valuable intelligence information. Such intelligence information must be in written form, consisting of at least 500 words or one page, to assess its value. The Commission on Audit (CoA) may also audit this intelligence information.

The existing duties and responsibilities of uniformed personnel can be amended to include cooperation in intelligence gathering.

Proposed Law #11

A law requiring all LGUs to have a website and a google drive or dropbox account

Main Goal: Transparency, people's participation and accountability

If all citizens can view all government documents, they can learn about government processes and contracts. Knowledge is a prerequisite for participative governance. With adequate knowledge, any citizen can become a politician.

3rd unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

Program of Government #9: To upload all the Ordinances, Contracts, Bill of Materials, Deed of Absolute Sale, Loan Agreements, Purchase Agreements, Case Studies and Empirical Data to the Official Website and FB Page.

Program of Government #10: To upload all the draft contracts and agreements A WEEK before the actual signing so that the citizen and experts can find irregularities and recommendations.

3rd unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

Program of Government #11: To stream live all the procurement activities in the FB Page and Official Website of LGU.

Program of Government #12: To install CCTV camera in the office of the Mayor that will be stream live 24/7 in the Official Website of LGU.

All meeting transcript of the President, Mayor, and Governor shall be uploaded in their respective Official Website.

4th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Minimum content of each LGU website:

- All ordinances ('local laws') and resolutions of every city, municipality, or province since the creation of local government or since 1991.
- Ordinances and resolutions attributable to each councilor. Each councilor should have a dedicated page listing the ordinances and resolutions they have created and passed, serving as their legacy. When ordinances and resolutions are publicly available, citizens can assess the quality of a councilor's ideas. This allows voters to determine whether the councilor's proposals are merely replicas of existing national laws or the work of other councilors.
- Appropriation ordinances for each item in the annual LGU budget can also be tracked and reviewed, improving accountability and transparency.
- Ordinances and resolutions should be filterable by year, month, and author.
- All COA reports since 1991.

Difficult to implement. It's just a proposal.

Minimum content of each LGU website:

- At least a one-page notarized résumé of all incumbent politicians and government officials earning more than Php 35,000 should be required. Some sections of the résumé may be redacted with a marker if confidential. However, any information already publicly available on Google, such as the name of the school or employer, should not be redacted.
- The SALN (Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth) of all public officials should be made available. If any data needs to be redacted, it may be redacted, provided that a written explanation is attached, stating the reason for the redaction.
- List of all departments in an LGU, their organizational structure, and the salary levels of each public official. The salary levels may be controversial, but they are funded by the people's taxes. While making this information public can be optional, it should be open for debate and discussion. By publicizing it, lawyers, civil service officials, and citizens can more easily identify any abuse of appointing authority. It can also help minimize ghost employees and allow any private citizen to compute the total operational budget of every LGU.

Difficult to implement. It's just a proposal.

Use of google drive and dropbox account

- All draft public documents and contracts can be placed in the google drive or dropbox.
- When the public document is final, it can be uploaded in the official website of every LGU.
- All the bidding documents in relation to Local Government Procurement Code can also be placed in the google drive or dropbox. Once a contract is awarded, there must be a one page for every government contract of more than P500,000 in the official website of every LGU.
- This proposed law is also applicable to other government entity such as agency, department, Government Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCC), etc...
- Proactive publication of government documents like Singapore. Better than Freedom of Information Law.
- An alternative to a Google Drive or Dropbox account is simply a Facebook page titled "Name of LGU + All Public Documents."

Proposed Law #11

A law requiring all public schools to have a website

Includes state universities, local universities, primary, secondary, and senior high schools.

Minimum content of each school website:

- The management committee
- All contracts in the implementation of the Local Government Procurement Law
- The tuition fees for all courses, with breakdown of fees
- The number of full time and part time teachers or professors
- A career page section for aspirant teachers or professors
- The enrollment process
- School guidelines and handbook

An Ivy League school-like website that is easy for students to navigate.

Proposed Law #12

A law allowing Commission on Audits (CoA) to recommend a case
directly to Sandiganbayan

“CoA does not have the legal power to prosecute corruption suspects, when an audit contains indications of corruption the case is transferred to the Ombudsman. Only the Ombudsman can bring people to court.”
(Mendoza, 2015)

5th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Recommendation

Public trials open to the media, like Senate and Congress hearings:

- For CoA disallowances of at least P500,000 with only one public official involved.
- For CoA disallowances of at least 10% of an annual LGU budget, the City Mayor, the chief accountant, and all councilors shall be automatically subpoenaed to explain the disallowance exceeding 10%.
- If the Sandiganbayan proves that corruption has indeed occurred, the Mayor and the Councilors shall be required to repay the entire disallowance. This can be enacted as a separate law, or an amendment to existing law.
- The statements of all the public officials involved shall be transcribed and made available in the public domain.
 - The transcribed written statement can be used for public policy and proposed law formulation. It can also be helpful for researchers, lawmakers, and deaf individuals.

“COA disallowance refers to a formal ruling by the Commission on Audit (COA) in the Philippines that a particular government expenditure is illegal, irregular, unnecessary, or excessive, and therefore must be refunded or returned by the responsible officials.”

Amendment to Existing Law

All graft cases involving more than PHP 500,000 shall have a maximum public trial duration of 60 days.

“Justice delayed is justice denied” – Prime Minister William Gladstone

6th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Amendment to Existing Law

Require all elective officials to work full time

Includes the President, Senators, Congressmen/Congresswomen, Mayors, Governors, Councilors and Board Members.

Working full-time can become a requirement to become a member of a strong political party.

7th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- Like any ordinary employee, elective public officials shall be required to work at least seven (7) hours per day and five days per week.
- They must have a designated login and logout time in the building where they work (e.g., City Hall for Mayors and Councilors).
- In cases of fieldwork where they need to engage with the public, a maximum of two days per week shall be allowed.
- For attending seminars, local and national events, public speaking engagements, etc., these activities must be properly recorded in a notebook or journal.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- A copy of the notebook or journal can be requested by any Filipino citizen. To reduce paper costs, it is highly recommended that a PDF copy of this journal be uploaded onto the respective official website (e.g., LGU websites for Mayors and Councilors).
- Similar to the concept of SALN and other government documents, there is no need to waste paper printing information that should be publicly accessible. Instead, why not scan these documents and upload them online as PDFs?
- All elected officials shall also be required to submit an accomplishment report every quarter.
- I came up with this proposed law after watching a trailer for the upcoming Metro Manila Film Festival (MMFF), in which some of the actors and actresses are incumbent governors and congressmen.

Penalty

- Pro-rated salary deductions based on number of days absent.
- Elective officials can be disqualified to hold public office if they are absent for more than 30 days per year.

Proposed Law #13

A law requiring the creation of General Appropriation Act (GAA) to be open, participative, and transparent.

One of the reasons why we need to require all elected public officials to work full-time is that the most important legislation (GAA) each year affects the education, lives, and future of many children.

Institutionalizing the process to include the following:

1. The creation of the General Appropriation Act shall be in one big room, open to the public, including the press.
2. The computer on which the draft of the General Appropriations Act is prepared shall be connected to a huge screen so that everyone in the room can see it.
3. There shall be a live Facebook or YouTube video of the entire process of adding or removing items in the General Appropriations Act.
4. At least 5 Certified Public Accountants and 5 Commission on Audit representatives must be present during the creation of the GAA.
5. All Congressmen, Senators, department heads, and offices (such as the Office of the President and Vice President), etc., who want to add a line of budget in the GAA shall have a minimum requirement.

Minimum requirements:

- A notarized affidavit of their itemized proposed budget. The proposed budget must have three required signatories: one CPA, one COA auditor (incumbent or retired), and one lawyer.
- A notarized accomplishment report of all past budget appropriations, including a list of successful and ongoing projects, pictures of the projects before and after, project details, etc. If a first-time senator or congressman, they are exempted from this requirement.
- Notarization improves accountability and monitoring. When it is notarized, it becomes public domain. It can be used to file a corruption case in case of an anomaly. Congressmen, senators, etc., will be less likely to add a ghost or anomalous project, as it can be tracked in the future.

Institutionalizing the process to include the following:

6. All the above notarized documents must be sent to a centralized email address with the following format: philippinegaa2025@gmail.com, philippinegaa2026@gmail.com, etc. Only one person shall be accountable for the password—either the head of the Senate Committee or the Secretary of the Department of Budget and Management.
7. All the above notarized documents must be reuploaded to a government website, Google Drive, or Dropbox folder open to all Filipinos.
8. Each itemized budget can be gradually added to the draft GAA after the recommendations of five CPAs and five COA representatives (who can also be CPAs or lawyers with experience working in COA).
9. The process of adding each notarized and individual budget shall be done on one computer only, recorded via YouTube or Facebook Live, and displayed on a big screen.
10. This can be a long and tiring process, but it will be worth it, ensuring that every peso of the taxpayers will not go to corruption.
11. I will improve this process in the future.

Proposed Law #14

A law requiring the creation of the Local Government Budget
to be open, participative, and transparent

Same process as the previous proposed law, but applicable in the local government.

Why create a different law? The process, stakeholders, committee members, and penalties are different at the national and local levels. If no national law is passed in the next three years, it can be passed as a local law or ordinance.

Proposed Law #15

A law banning all elected and appointed officials to travel abroad during their term

Same process as the previous proposed law, but applicable in the local government.

Why create a different law? The process, stakeholders, committee members, and penalties are different at the national and local levels. If no national law is passed in the next three years, it can be passed as a local law or ordinance.

Proposed Law #15

A law banning all elected and appointed officials to travel abroad during their term

A law banning all elected and appointed officials to travel abroad or out-of-town
during a natural calamity

I watched an interview with Mayor Vico Sotto where he said that he didn't travel abroad during his term. We can institutionalize this idea.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- The Bureau of Immigration (BI) should prohibit all elective officials from traveling abroad.
- Any public official of BI who allows elected and appointed officials to travel abroad shall face a penalty equal to one month's salary.
- Other government officials (such as public school teachers, public nurses, local government employees, etc.) can travel abroad a maximum of twice per year, with a limit of 15 days per trip.
- For local politicians: Two weeks before and after of a natural calamity such as typhoon and earthquake.

Penalty

- 1st offense: One-month salary
- 2nd offense: Two-month salary
- 3rd offense: Three-month salary
- 4th offense: Ban from holding public office for the next three years. If a Mayor or Governor, they will be succeeded by the Vice Mayor or Vice Governor, respectively.
- *Other option: First three offense can be skipped.*

**It is a matter of life and death for their constituents,
so why go abroad or out of town?**

Proposed Law #16

A law requiring the usage of negotiation table in all government negotiation

Applicable to the President, Mayor, Governor, Barangay Captain, Councilor, etc. This will ensure that our government is negotiating on behalf of the greater good. It must be open, recorded, and transparent.

8th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Open, recorded, and transparent

- One lawyer and executive secretary must be present
- The lawyer shall ensure that both parties (the official and the other person) have negotiations within the boundaries of the law
- The executive secretary shall prepare the minutes of the meeting
- Audio recording is required. Video recording is optional.
- The audio recording shall be kept by the Information Technology Department. The public official must also have an audio recording of the negotiations in case they are summoned by the competent court.
- All the minutes of the meetings shall be notarized every quarter. Signed by the representative of the government (President, Mayor, Governor, etc...), executive secretary and the lawyer.

Goal

- Eradicate under-the-table transactions
- Avoid transactions outside the negotiation table or outside the office of the official
- Ensure that the government is negotiating on behalf of the greater good

Penalty

All negotiations not conducted at the negotiation table shall be considered invalid.

Proposed Law #17

A law adopting the transparency mechanism of Singapore

Applicable to the following:

- Local Government Unit (City and Province. Except barangay, unless there is an ordinance)
- Office of the President and Vice President (two separate website)
- Each senator and each representative
- Departments, Bureaus, GOCC, etc...

9th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Proactive approach

Proactive approach to publicizing information on a specific website like <https://www.parliament.gov.sg/>

Provision

Require usage of the <https://www.parliament.gov.sg/> as the website template

The legislative power of Singapore is vested in the Legislature which consists of the President and Parliament. The Parliament of Singapore is unicameral.

ANNOUNCEMENT

Parliament will be sitting from 4 March to 10 March 2025 (excluding Saturday and Sunday). Sitting on 4 March 2025 will commence at 11.00 am.

On sitting days, the livestream of Parliament proceedings can be viewed on MDDI's YouTube channel at this [link](#).

The list of MPs speaking will be available on [Parliament of Singapore's](#) official Facebook page.

Please click the links on the right to access the various Parliamentary Business items.

Official Reports (Parl Debates)

Votes and Proceedings

Standing Orders

**Select Committee on Deliberate Online
Falsehoods – Causes, Consequences
and Countermeasures**

Select Committee Reports

Order Papers

Glossary

Bills Introduced

Papers Presented to Parliament

**Committee of Privileges - Complaint
Against Ms Raeesah Khan**

ANNOUNCEMENT

Parliament will be sitting from 4 March to 10 March 2025 (excluding Saturday and Sunday). Sitting on 4 March 2025 will commence at 11.00 am.

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The list of MPs speaking will be available on [Parliament of Singapore's](#) official Facebook page.

Proposed Law #18

An act institutionalizing that a treaty or international agreement can only be void and invalid if concurred in by at least two-thirds of all Members of the Senate.

According to the Section 21 of Article VII of the 1987 Constitution,

“No treaty or international agreement shall be valid and effective unless concurred in by at least two-thirds of all the Members of the Senate.”

- I watched the interview of Bam Aquino and Karen Davila, and one of the questions was about the withdrawal of the Philippines from the ICC. Karen Davila asked, “Should the Philippines rejoin the ICC?”
- Many experts have also said that we didn’t withdraw because the President alone cannot unilaterally withdraw from treaties.
- Karen Davila should have asked, “Do you think the President alone can unilaterally withdraw from treaties?” My answer is no, because if we allow that, any unreasonable and tyrannical leader could easily withdraw from treaties.
- So, back to the title of the proposed law - we need at least a supermajority (2/3 votes of all members of the Senate) to withdraw from treaties. If the Constitution is silent about it, then we need to enact a law.

Proposed Law #19

A law limiting property ownership for all Filipinos who have been politicians

Same idea of Comprehensive Agrarian Reform Law and Balikbayan Law

For politicians: Maximum of three properties only

- Principal Residence
- Secondary Property (Lot investment or rest house)
- Additional Property near the government office

Maximum total of 1500sqm. Provided 500sqm each of above properties

FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

The Moneylender and his Wife by Quinten Metsys (1514)

Proposed Law #1

A law banning any form of lump sum that cannot be audited or tracked by the
Commission on Audit (CoA)

All expenses shall have a receipt such as BIR service invoice, and notarized acknowledgement receipt.

Eradicate the “Liquidation by Certification”.

Other option: Set amount or item that can be excluded from the liquidation by certification.

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring the Commission on Audit (CoA) to give a perceived corruption index (PCI)

Includes the following:

- Every LGU (City and province, except barangay)
- Every members of congress (senate and representatives)
- Office of the President and Vice President (two separate PCI)
- All GOCC
- All Departments such as DPWH, DOH, etc...
- Or any government entity with more than 50 Million annual budget

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- The Ombudsman lawyers, within three months after the publication of CoA reports, shall be required to investigate LGUs, agencies, GOCCs, government offices, etc., that belong to the lowest 30% of PCI rankings.
- The PCI can also be used as the basis for the National Tax Allocations (NTA):
 - Those that belong into the lowest 30% shall not have a budget increase in the next year.
 - Those that belong into the highest 20% shall be rewarded with a budget increase.
 - The budget increase or decrease will not depend on the caprice of any politician or political party but will be based on the results of CoA reports.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

The final PCI can also be an **average of multiple important PCI:**

- PCI based on overall disallowances by CoA
- PCI based on government efficiency in the salaries of government officials
- PCI based on government contracts and projects as per the Government Procurement Code of the Philippines
- PCI based on the overall implementation of financial best practices and standards

Aside from averaging, we can also assign weights to the most and least important PCI. The above list can be improved after comprehensive research conducted by at least five (5) Certified Public Accountants, each with at least five (5) years of experience working in CoA.

Goal of PCI

- The Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) gives awards to some LGUs despite the latter having numerous CoA disallowances. There must be a basis for such awards, and one possible basis could be the PCI.
- The PCI can be used as a criterion by some voters when deciding whether to reelect an incumbent politician. We can assist the LCE and other pro good-governance politician in their next reelection if their PCI is very good.
- There should be a perpetual disqualification from public office for all Local Chief Executives (LCEs), such as mayors and governors, who belong to the lowest 5%. I believe they are the most corrupt and are unaware of what's happening with the financial aspect of their local government.
- We can improve our overall PCI next year worldwide with this kind of system. There would be no poverty in a country without corruption.

Proposed Law #3

A law requiring Standard Project Billboard of all government projects that can easily be tracked by Commission on Audit (CoA)

All government projects worth more than P500,000 shall have Standard Project Billboard, unless the price is otherwise specified by CoA.

Require all politicians, government officials, and contractor to have a group picture with the Standard Project Billboard as the background.

They must take ownership to the success and failure of the project.

BLACK TEXT

CONSTRUCTION OF (Name of Project and Location)

CONTRACTOR _____

DATE STARTED _____

CONTRACT COMPLETION DATE _____

CONTRACT COST _____

CONSTRUCTION CONSULTANT _____

IMPLEMENTING OFFICE _____

SOURCE OF FUND _____

DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS

Text 2920 or call (32) 185-62 for any concerns on this project
www.dpwh.gov.ph

WHITE BACKGROUND

NOTE: For source of fund, state if DPWH Regular Budget, Priority Development Assistance Fund, CapEx/OpEx/DRR Budget, Calamity Fund, MMAC Fund, etc.
The Layout of Project Billboard was based on D.O. 141 Series 2016

DPWH STANDARD PROJECT BILLBOARD

DPWH Cavite I District Engineering Office
Brgy. De Ocampo Trade Martines City Cavite

Project: _____

Location: _____ Cost: _____
Fund/Source/s: _____

Implementing Agencies: _____
Development Partner/s: _____
Contractor/s: _____
Brief Description of Project: _____

Project

Number	Project Name	Project Status				Remarks
		Budget	Actual Cost	Remaining	Disbursed	

For projects or contracts where the project development is approved by a higher authority, please indicate the authority.

DPWH Regional Office/Province: _____
 Address: _____
 Contact No.: _____ or Toll-Free DPWH Office Number 2911-821987

WHITE BACKGROUND

COA BILLBOARD

QR Code with Important Details

All stakeholders that includes the following:

- city councilor or board member who introduced the project in the regular session
- quality engineers of the project
- CPA of the project

Project status and metrics that complies with the best project management principle. Whether the project is over the budget, under the budget, behind the schedule, ahead the schedule, etc...

FAIR ELECTION

Opening session of the General Assembly, 5 May 1789, by Auguste Couder (1839)

Proposed Law #1

A law banning all forms of subsidy to voters one year before election

Includes AKAP, TUPAD, AICS, etc...

Those neophyte aspirant politicians or opposition politicians with no government funds will have a small chance of winning against incumbent politicians who can use multi-million or even billion-peso government funds.

Exception: Those that are properly documented under the relevant agencies, such as the DSWD, DOH, etc.

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring at least three public debates for all Mayor and Governor aspirants

National power is decentralized to Local Government Units. We should give importance to local debates just as we give importance to presidential debates.

Schedule of public local debates:

- First week of the campaign period
- Middle week of the campaign period
- Last week of the campaign period

11th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

I used the term “at least three public debates”. The more, the better - such as holding public debates every week during the campaign period. We can minimize the use of campaign funds if COMELEC and other reputable civic organizations organize fair and public local debates.

We can follow the same presidential debate format but focus on problems and issues at the local level.

Penalty: Automatic disqualification for failure to attend public debates. If there is a valid medical reason, a letter from a licensed doctor must indicate the medical condition.

Proposed Law #2a

A law requiring at least three public debates for
all City Councilor and Provincial Member Aspirants

National power is decentralized to Local Government Units. We should give importance to local debates just as we give importance to presidential debates.

Schedule of public local debates:

- First week of the campaign period
- Middle week of the campaign period
- Last week of the campaign period

11th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Proposed Law #2b

A law requiring all national-level aspirants, such as the President, Vice President, Senators, and Congressman/Congresswoman, to participate in a national public debate.

Schedule of public local debates:

- First week of the campaign period
- Middle week of the campaign period
- Last week of the campaign period

Penalty: Automatic disqualification for failure to attend public debates. If there is a valid medical reason, a letter from a licensed doctor must indicate the medical condition.

11th unorthodox solution to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Proposed Law #3

A law banning all forms of advertisements outside the election campaign period

Outside the election campaign period **includes the days before and after** the filing of the Certificate of Candidacy (COC).

The title is already clear and obvious; I just wanted to reiterate.

TOP AD SPENDERS ON TV, RADIO, PRINT, AND BILLBOARDS

January to December 2024 (Based on published rated cards)

Source: Nielsen Ad Intel

Image screenshot from Philippine Center for Investigative Journalism (PCIJ)
Data Source: Nielsen Ad Intel | Bar Chart Race by Flourish Studio

TOP AD SPENDERS ON TV, RADIO, PRINT, AND BILLBOARDS

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NATIONAL NEWS

Resolving classroom shortage may take over 20 years – EDCOM report

By *Ashzel Hachero* ⌚ January 31, 2025

EDCOM2
The Second Congressional
Commission on Education

Image screenshot from Malaya Business Insight. Report from Congressional Commission on Education

The election is not fair if some politician aspirants can spend anywhere from a hundred million to a billion even before the start of the election campaign, while others have minimal budget.

If these aspirants have a platform, they can simply notarize it and publicize it on their official Facebook page. Any Filipino can create a centralized repository for these platforms, such as a website, google drive, or Dropbox, which can be easily analyzed and downloaded by all Filipino voters.

The best way to learn more about the aspirants and their platforms is through a public debate organized by COMELEC, local COMELEC offices, TV stations, or any reputable organization. It requires minimal expense and helps make the election fair for all aspirants.

Penalty

Aspirants who spend ads outside campaign period shall have a penalty equivalent to their campaign ad expenditures.

If an aspirant spends one billion, they shall have a penalty equivalent to one billion, payable to the Republic of the Philippines within 30 days. Failure to pay via bank transfer, with an electronic receipt as proof of payment, shall incur an interest of 5% per month.

The medium of advertisement, such as TV stations, radio, billboard providers, and print media, shall also be penalized 50% of the campaign ad expenditure to prevent the excuse that the ads were sponsored by friends or family.

Proposed Law #4

A law improving the election counting process

At least 10% of the barangays in a city and at least 10% of the cities in a province must be manually counted.

The selection of barangays and cities shall be done randomly **AFTER** the transmission of votes to the main server.

Once at least 10% of the barangays and cities are randomly chosen, the manual counting shall commence immediately.

If manual counting cannot start because of exhaustion after a whole day election, all precincts under the 10% barangays and 10% cities shall be locked and heavily guarded by police officers and volunteered Filipinos.

The manual counting can start the next day after election.

Recommendation to the existing process of
Parish Pastoral Council for Responsible Voting (PPCRV)

Proposed Law #3

Random Selection of Election Returns to be counted manually after the COMELEC publishes the official Pro and Con of the Election Result.

At the City and Municipal Level ^{Based on 10% Rate}
10% of the total barangays in each City and Municipality shall be selected randomly for manual counting.

Depending on the budget allocated, the 10% can be rounded up or down. I suggest though, rounded up. However, it can be expensive instead of rounding down.

Example: In a City with 18 barangays.

10% of 18 barangays is 1.8 barangays.

If rounded up, 2 barangays shall be counted manually.

Distribution of the Randomness:

In a transparent jar, the names of all the barangays shall be written in a 1/4 sheet of paper.

There shall be a failure of election if the ^{result in the} 10% barangay in a given City or Municipality is different to the result publicized by the COMELEC.

~~Other City or Municipality~~

The result of other City and Municipality ~~will~~ shall not be affected, as long as the result of the 10% barangay is the same to the result publicized by the COMELEC.

The remaining 90% of the barangay shall be subject to MANUAL Counting if the 10% barangay has ~~irregularity~~ irregularity based on the manual counting.

For Cities and Municipalities in which 90% of the barangay is subjected to manual counting because of the irregularities of 10% barangay, the result of the Total Manual Counting (10% +) shall be declared the official Result.

Proposed Law #5

A law making TV Ads fair to all Filipinos

Only applicable to those candidates that needs national awareness

Such as President, Vice President and Senators

The election is not fair if some candidates can spend P500 Million to P2 Billion like they are in a shopping spree, while some Filipino candidates frugally spend their limited resources.

Proposed Law #6

A law instituting Fair Debate Framework with Questions from the Citizens

The election is not fair if some candidates can spend P500 Million to P2 Billion like they are in a shopping spree, while some Filipino candidates frugally spend their limited resources.

I created the paper called “City Mayor Fair Debate Framework with Questions by the Filipino Citizens”.

GOVERNMENT PROJECTS

Image Source: **7 Zoom Level** Google Map (2025)

Image Source: **7 Zoom Level** Google Map (2025)

Proposed Law #1

A law increasing the minimum wage to P300 per hour

“A living wage is defined as a wage sufficient to provide the necessities and comforts essential to an acceptable standard of living. An individual working 40 hours per week would be able to afford food, child care, medical, housing, transportation and other expenses for his family.” - Mel Wilson, manager of NASW’s Department of Social Justice and Human Rights

EMPLOYEE RIGHTS

UNDER THE FAIR LABOR STANDARDS ACT

FEDERAL MINIMUM WAGE

\$7.25 PER HOUR

BEGINNING JULY 24, 2009

Image source: Department of Labor poster of United States of America

Priority Level

- High Priority – to be implemented within the next three years
- Medium Priority – to be implemented within the next six years
- Low Priority – to be implemented after both high and medium priority

High Priority

- Construction worker of government civil projects such as schools, public roads, government facilities, etc...
- All public-school teachers, school officials and personnel
- All public officials in public hospitals
- All public officials in BIR, Pag-IBIG, etc... (specially client facing job)
- Fast food chains such as Jollibee, McDo, etc...

Medium Priority

- All Filipinos working in the banking and finance industry
- All Filipinos working in Supermarkets such as SM, Robinsons, etc...
- All government officials regardless of status (whether regular, job order or contractual)
- All Filipinos working in a company or businesses with at least 50 million annual income

We cannot increase the minimum wage to everyone, but we can gradually increase it for different job types, sectors, and businesses.

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring all provinces, cities, and municipalities to have
at least one Project Management Professional (PMP)

The PMP must update the public on the progress of all projects (initiated, ongoing, and completed).

They must work closely with an IT professional for pull communication.

Pull communication is a passive form of communication in which information is made available to stakeholders via intranet, e-learning, and knowledge repositories (Project Management Institute, 2021).

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- The IT professional is required to publish updates weekly on the LGU's official website.
- Meanwhile, the PMP must update the public quarterly on the LGU's official Facebook page and upload the updates to the official website.
- The PMP should not be appointed by an incumbent elected official. One month after the election, the position should be opened to the public. The Regional CSC (Civil Service Commission), DILG (Department of the Interior and Local Government), or DPWH (Department of Public Works and Highways) can hire the PMP on behalf of the provinces. If there are not enough PMPs for all LGU in the Philippines, any engineer or professional with at least three years of experience in project management may fill the position.

Implementing Rules and Regulation (part of)

- The minimum salary of a PMP should be ₱50,000 to ₱80,000 per month, depending on the available resources of the LGU (city, municipality, or province).
- While the hiring authority can be the CSC, DILG, or DPWH, the funds should come from the LGU.
- We can require that all DPWH office must have at least one Project Management Professional.
 - DPWH Regional Office (Portfolio Manager, must be PMP)
 - DPWH Provincial Office (Portfolio Manager, must be PMP)
 - DPWH City and Municipality Office (Project Manager, must be PMP)

Goal of PMP for every LGU except Barangay

- Proactively inform the public whether the projects are on time and on budget, independent of the influence or control of the elected officials.
- Improve project's quality and efficiency.
- Reduce defect and repeat job.

Additional Recommendation

- All LGUs should be required to have at least one PMP for every ₱500 million of their annual budget.
- For an LGU with an annual budget of ₱1.5 billion, there must be a minimum of three PMPs.

Proposed Law #3

A law on the standardization of school building prices

According to DepEd Assistant Secretary Tonisito Umali (2012), “Actually, a single-story classroom with a toilet, furniture, and fixtures costs ₱730,000, while a two-story classroom with a toilet, furniture, and fixtures costs ₱1.25 million. The reason the average cost of a classroom in a two-story building is higher is that the columns, foundations, and overall architectural and engineering structure are different and need to be stronger.”

According to Education Undersecretary Epimaco V. Densing III (2023), the average cost of a classroom is ₱2.5 million.

The Department of Budget and Management (DBM) approved the release of ₱5.83 billion to help build 1,834 classrooms (Dela Cruz, 2024).

₱5.83 billion / 1834 = ₱3.178 million per classroom

No data in the article specifies the classroom size in square meters, whether it includes land acquisition, or whether the classroom is furnished.

The price should be based on a bottom-up estimate with a bill of materials.

Engineers in the DPWH must establish a standardized price for each classroom, considering the number of stories in the building. All designs and drawings must be standardized, centralized, and made available on the DPWH website so that contractors and officials can access them free of charge. In the long run, making these resources available on the DPWH website could save more than one billion pesos.

Republic of the Philippines
 DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
 EDUCATION FACILITIES DIVISION
 Meralco Avenue, Pasig City

BUDGETARY ESTIMATE

Annex A

PREPARATION OF MID-RISE SCHOOL BUILDING PLANS AND DESIGNS

SCHOOL BUILDING	NUMBER OF CLASSROOMS		CLASSROOMS WITH WORKSHOPS	TOTAL CONSTRUCTION COST	Recommended Professional Fee (RPF) for Detailed Architectural and Engineering Design Services (DAEDS)	TOTAL RECOMMENDED PROFESSIONAL FEE	CLASSROOMS WITH WORKSHOPS	TOTAL CONSTRUCTION COST	ADDITIONAL FEE	ADDITIONAL FEE (STANDARD ACADEMIC SCHOOL BUILDING DESIGN WITH WORKSHOP)
FIVE (5) - STOREY	25	CLASSROOMS	19CL, 3 WORKSHOP	50,294,200.00	3M plus 5% of excess of 50M	3,014,710.00	19CL, 3 WORKSHOP	50,294,200.00	0.10%	50,294.20
	20	CLASSROOMS	14CL, 3 WORKSHOP						0.10%	50,294.20
SIX (6) - STOREY	30	CLASSROOMS	22CL, 4 WORKSHOP	60,255,250.00	3M plus 5% of excess of 50M	3,512,762.50	22CL, 4 WORKSHOP	60,255,250.00	0.10%	60,255.25
	24	CLASSROOMS	18CL, 3 WORKSHOP						0.10%	60,255.25
SEVEN (7) - STOREY	35	CLASSROOMS	27CL, 4 WORKSHOP	70,216,300.00	3M plus 5% of excess of 50M	4,010,815.00	27CL, 4 WORKSHOP	70,216,300.00	0.10%	70,216.30
	28	CLASSROOMS	22CL, 3 WORKSHOP						0.10%	70,216.30
EIGHT (8) - STOREY	40	CLASSROOMS	30CL, 5 WORKSHOP	80,177,350.00	3M plus 5% of excess of 50M	4,508,867.50	30CL, 5 WORKSHOP	80,177,350.00	0.10%	80,177.35
	32	CLASSROOMS	24CL, 4 WORKSHOP						0.10%	80,177.35

NINE (9) - STOREY	45	CLASSROOMS	33CL, 6 WORKSHOP	90,138,400.00	3M plus 5% of excess of 50M	5,006,920.00	33CL, 6 WORKSHOP	90,138,400.00	0.10%	90,138.40
	36	CLASSROOMS	26CL, 5 WORKSHOP						0.10%	90,138.40
TEN (10) - STOREY	50	CLASSROOMS	36CL, 7 WORKSHOP	100,099,450.00	5.5 plus 4% of excess of 100M	5,503,978.00	36CL, 7 WORKSHOP	100,099,450.00	0.10%	100,099.45
	40	CLASSROOMS	30CL, 5 WORKSHOP						0.10%	100,099.45
ELEVEN (11) - STOREY	55	CLASSROOMS	39CL, 8 WORKSHOP	110,549,450.00	5.5 plus 4% of excess of 100M	5,921,978.00	39CL, 8 WORKSHOP	110,549,450.00	0.10%	110,549.45
	44	CLASSROOMS	30CL, 7 WORKSHOP						0.10%	110,549.45
TWELVE (12) - STOREY	60	CLASSROOMS	42CL, 9 WORKSHOP	120,999,450.00	5.5 plus 4% of excess of 100M	6,339,978.00	42CL, 9 WORKSHOP	120,999,450.00	0.10%	120,999.45
	48	CLASSROOMS	36CL, 7 WORKSHOP						0.10%	120,999.45
SUB-TOTAL						37,820,009.00				1,365,459.70

Image: Budgetary Estimate Adapted from Annex A: Standard building design, by Department of Education, 2019

The professional fee is the standard fee for architects and engineers.

If we standardize the design and pricing across the entire Philippines, we can save on professional fees in the long term.

The total construction cost for the previous example is:

$\text{₱}50,294,200 + \text{₱}60,255,250 + \text{₱}70,216,300 + \text{₱}80,177,350 + \text{₱}90,138,400 + \text{₱}100,099,450 + \text{₱}110,549,450 + \text{₱}120,999,450 = \text{₱}682,729,850.$

The total recommended professional fee for the previous example is $\text{₱}37,820,009$, which is approximately 5.54% of the total cost.

This money can be used to hire project management professional and civil engineers that can implement the existing and standardize designs. It can also be used to build additional classrooms or for land procurement.

REPUBLIC OF THE PHILIPPINES

DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC WORKS AND HIGHWAYS

RIGHT PROJECT, RIGHT COST, RIGHT QUALITY, RIGHT ON TIME, RIGHT PEOPLE

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References ▾

REFERENCES

DPWH Atlas
StreamMS
Laws, Codes, Orders
Guidelines, Manuals
Standard Design
Reports
Issuances

Standard Design Plans for School Buildings

Attachment	Size
Standard Design Plans for One (1) Storey School Buildings (1,2,3,4 and 5 Classrooms)	46.65 MB
Standard Design Plans for Two (2) Storey School Buildings (6 and 12 Classrooms)	30.42 MB
Old Standard Design Plans for Two (2) Storey School Buildings (8 Classrooms)	7.43 MB

Image: Screenshot of Standard Design Plans for School Buildings by Department of Public Works and Highways

Proposed Law #4

A law on the standardization of all infrastructure projects prices

Includes public hospitals, major roads, farm-to-market roads, bridges, LGU buildings, etc...

Set maximum price for the bare type and furnished rooms.

Set maximum price for nth storey building at x sqm.

Set maximum price for the road cost per square km.

Proposed Law #5

A law requiring all LGUs to adopt the flood control detention tank in BGC

Purchase multiple vacant lots of at least 300sqm across the Philippines for the flood control detention tank. All the nearby canals should flow here.

The head of engineering office should hire a civil engineer or project management professional to spearhead the construction of this project.

Source of Funds

- Every LGU with at least P100 million annual budget
- General Appropriations Act every year should prioritize projects like this

GMA Integrated News/Facebook

BANTAY BUDGET 2025

Php 248.07 Bilyon

Ito ang halaga ng pondong inaprubahan para sa ***Flood Management Program*** ng DPWH sa taong 2025.

Mas mataas ito kumpara sa Php 244 Bilyong pondo noong 2024.

Source: General Appropriations Act of 2025, DBM

BANTAY BUDGET 2025

CONSTRUCTION/MAINTENANCE OF FLOOD MITIGATION FACILITIES WITHIN MAJOR RIVER BASINS AND PRINCIPAL RIVERS

REGION	AMOUNT in Php
NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION	85,686,598,000
ILOCOS	2,070,000,000
CORDILLERA	617,487,000
CAGAYAN VALLEY	315,000,000
CENTRAL LUZON	1,089,882,000
CALABARZON	1,160,000,000
MIMAROPA	421,271,000
BICOL	139,900,000
WESTERN VISAYAS	234,750,000
CENTRAL VISAYAS	326,139,000
EASTERN VISAYAS	483,737,000
ZAMBOANGA PENINSULA	488,761,000
NORTHERN MINDANAO	150,000,000
DAVAO	85,000,000
SOCCKSARGEN	302,000,000
CARAGA	70,000,000

Source: General Appropriations Act of 2025, DBM

Image Source: Kaya Natin

Data Source: General Appropriations Act of 2025

Proposed Law #6

A law setting the minimum number of age of major government building
before it can be demolished to construct a new one

Includes the following:

City Hall

Municipal Hall

Provincial Hall

Senate Building Hall

Public Hospitals

Proposed Minimum Requirements

- After a thorough debate among engineers and architects, we must set an age nationwide for when to demolish and build new major government buildings.
- There must be a risk-benefit analysis to justify whether a major government building should be rebuilt or just simply renovated.
- There are some city halls that can cost more than 250 million to 1 billion pesos.
- We must first ensure that all children and adults who dream of going to school are in school.
- At least 98% of children and adults, with ages applicable for school, should be in school.

Example: The Singapore City Hall was built in 1929 and renovated in 1987 and 2015, with gaps of 58 and 28 years, respectively. It was just renovated and not rebuilt. Singaporeans have used it for more than 96 years.

Proposed Law #7

A law banning the destruction of roads only to be rebuilt

Build adequate schools and hospitals before destroying roads.

Only certain parts of the roads that needs to be fixed should be repaired, not the entire barangay or city roads.

Penalty: Perpetual disqualification to public office to those public and elected officials behind the destruction of roads.

Opportunity Cost

According to Investopedia, opportunity cost is the forgone benefit that would have been derived from an option other than the one that was chosen.

Opportunity Cost of Road Destructions

100 million worth of roads in a major City

P5,000 per semester for a scholarship

Four years require eight(8) semesters

A student needs P40,000 to earn a degree for this scholarship

$100 \text{ million} / P40,000 = 2,500$

2,500 students can be the children of a farmer, a fisherman, a tricycle/pedicab/jeepney driver, a factory worker, a street wiper, etc., or any Filipino parents who have been poor their entire lives and whose only hope for a brighter future is their children.

CORRUPTION IS PAID BY THE POOR
- Pope Francis

Image by anonymous (n.d.)

All proposed laws, if they cannot be passed at the national level due to politics, political dynasty or a lack of majority votes, may become local ordinances applicable to any local government unit, such as a city, municipality, or province.

ERADICATION OF POLITICAL DYNASTY

Jacques-Louis David and Georges Rouget - The Coronation of Napoleon (1805)

CONFIRMATION BIAS

Confirmation bias is a cognitive bias where people have a tendency to search out, interpret, or even recall information in a way that reinforces preexisting beliefs.

Examples of Confirmation Bias

Not seeking out
objective facts

Interpreting information to
support your existing belief

Only remembering details
that uphold your belief

Ignoring information that
challenges your belief

Republic of the Philippines
SANGGUNIANG PANLUNGSOD
City Government of Pasig

Ordinance No. 37
Series of 2018

AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.

Authored by: Councilor Victor Ma. Regis N. Sotto
Co-Authored by: Councilors Rodrigo B. Asilo, Ferdinand A. Avis, Regino S. Balderrama, Orlando R. Benito, Rhichie Gerard T. Brown, Mario C. Concepcion, Jr., Rosalio D. Martires, Corazon M. Raymundo, Gregorio P. Rupisan, Jr., Alejandro E. Santiago, Wilfredo F. Sityar, LIGA Pres. Rigor J. Enriquez and SK Fed. President Georgia Lynne P. Clemente

First Page of the Freedom of Information Ordinance in
Pasig City Government, 2018, *City Ordinance No. 37, s. 2018*

Section 19. Penalties. Failure of any government official or employee to comply with the provisions of this Ordinance shall be a ground for the following penalties:

1st Offense:	Reprimand;
2nd Offense:	Suspension of five (5) to thirty (30) days; and
3rd Offense:	Dismissal from the service.

Page 10 of the Freedom of Information Ordinance in
Pasig City Government, 2018, *City Ordinance No. 37, s. 2018*

Strategy #1: Pass as a Local Ordinance

Adopt the proposed bill of former Senator Miriam Defensor Santiago titled
“The Anti-Political Dynasty Act”

Legislative Status:
Pending in the Committee (8/24/2011)

Section 4 of the Proposed Law

Persons Covered:

Prohibited Candidates. - No spouse, or person related within the second degree of consanguinity or affinity whether legitimate or illegitimate, to an incumbent elective official seeking reelection shall be allowed to hold or run for any elective office in the same province in the same election.

In case the constituency of the incumbent elective official is national in character, the above relatives shall be disqualified from running only within the same province where the former is a registered voter

Source: <https://legacy.senate.gov.ph/lisdata/106169091!.pdf>

Proposed Amendment

Scoring system that will be accepted by COMELEC.

The scoring system includes employee-like requirements such as educational background, experience, platforms, published papers, organizations, etc.

The candidate with the highest score will be accepted by COMELEC for candidacy.

Family members can just decide among themselves who should run.

Strategy #2: Political Will of the President, Mayor and Governor

As President of the Country:

Do not pass the GAA without the passage of important laws like the Freedom of Information Act and The Anti-Political Dynasty Act

As Mayor or Governor:

Do not pass the annual budget without the passage or adaptation of important ordinance like the Freedom of Information Act and The Anti-Political Dynasty Act

Strategy #3: Sign and Notarize an Affidavit of Declaration before Election

As President, Mayor or Governor:

An affidavit declaring that the first law or ordinance you will sign on your first day in office will be the Freedom of Information Act and the Anti-Political Dynasty Act

Take a recorded video in a law office in front of a lawyer that you will pass the Freedom of Information Act and the Anti-Political Dynasty Act. Publicize in your Official Facebook Account.

Strategy #3: Sign and Notarize an Affidavit of Declaration before Election

As Senator, Representative, Councilor and Provincial Board Member:

An affidavit declaring that the first law or ordinance you will sign on your first day in office will be the Freedom of Information Act and the Anti-Political Dynasty Act

Take a recorded video in a law office in front of a lawyer that you will pass the Freedom of Information Act and the Anti-Political Dynasty Act. Publicize in your Official Facebook Account.

Submit the Notarized Affidavit in the relevant office

It will be considered as a “Yes” vote in favor of the passage of

- Freedom of Information Act (at the national level)
- Freedom of Information Ordinance (at the local level)

- Anti-Political Dynasty Act (at the national level)
- Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance (at the local level)

We can also implement this kind of strategy in other important laws and ordinances in the future. Notarized an affidavit before election, and it’s considered as a “Yes” vote once elected.

Goal

Risk reduction

Eradicate empty promises

Filter the good vs the bad politicians

Eradicate corruption and political dynasty

A “yes” vote to important laws and ordinances even before the election

It is easy to file a Certificate of Candidacy (COC), but it is difficult to sign an Affidavit of Declaration against the personal interest.

List of proposed laws that have the potential to eradicate political dynasty in the Philippines

Proposed Law #1

A law requiring all political candidates to explain all their platforms in one whole day

This can change the political arena during the campaign period. It can drastically reduce the campaign funds.

Any ordinary citizen with no huge campaign funds can have the whole three years in preparation for this one important day. Holding an elective position should be a full-time job, as the lives or the quality of life of many citizens are at stake.

The quality of ideas presented in this one-day presentation of the platform can somehow give the voters a glimpse of the kind of government we can have under his/her leadership.

Politics can be reduced, as sometimes or somehow politics is often affected by the passions and desires of the aspirant's supporters.

In this one-day presentation of the platform, the focus will be the endurance, the determination, and the quality of ideas of the political aspirant. We will end up producing many platforms and many quality politicians in the future. I believe that not all members of a political dynasty can stand on their own feet and can produce original ideas.

Proposed Law #2

A law improving the selection process and minimum requirements
of the ombudsman and Judicial and Bar Council

I believe that the Ombudsman and the members of the Judicial and Bar Council should be highly independent people. What if there is an anomaly involving the incumbent President and Vice President? Like the more than 2 billion in intelligence and confidential funds every year? Why can't they investigate where the funds go? We must have an independent Ombudsman and Sandiganbayan to have a strong government. In another country, like South Korea, if the President or any high-ranking official is involved in any corruption scandal, their Supreme Prosecutors' Office can start an investigation.

We should adopt the system of South Korea in prosecuting high government officials. In the Philippines, both Senators and the House of Representatives, in “aid of legislation”, can investigate corruption

However, even though they accuse others, they themselves may be guilty. An example is the case of former Chief Justice Renato Corona, in which one of the issues was the incorrect declaration of SALN. The majority of the senators who rendered a “guilty” verdict may not have faithfully submitted their SALNs at all.

Proposed Law #3

A law providing an automatic minimum budget to the
Office of the Ombudsman and the Sandiganbayan Court

The executive branch can lower or raise the budget of the Office of the Ombudsman and the Sandiganbayan Court, a process that may, in some way, influence their decisions. By having a minimum allocated budget, their decisions will not be influenced. The average budget of the Office of the Ombudsman over the past three years shall be the minimum annual budget. It can only be increased but shall never be decreased. The same concept will be applied to the Sandiganbayan Court.

CORRUPTION PERCEPTIONS INDEX 2023

The perceived levels of public sector corruption in 180 countries/territories around the world.

SCORE COUNTRY/TERRITORY

90	Denmark
87	Finland
85	New Zealand
84	Norway
83	Singapore
82	Sweden
82	Switzerland
79	Netherlands
78	Germany
78	Luxembourg
77	Ireland
76	Canada
76	Estonia
75	Australia
75	Hong Kong
73	Belgium
73	Japan
73	Uruguay
72	Iceland
71	Austria
71	France
71	Seychelles
71	United Kingdom
69	Barbados
69	United States
68	Bhutan

68	United Arab Emirates
67	Taiwan
66	Chile
64	Bahamas
64	Cabo Verde
63	Korea, South
62	Israel
61	Lithuania
61	Portugal
60	Latvia
60	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
60	Spain
59	Botswana
58	Qatar
57	Czechia
56	Dominica
56	Italy
56	Slovenia
55	Costa Rica
55	Saint Lucia
54	Poland
54	Slovakia
53	Cyprus
53	Georgia
53	Grenada
53	Rwanda

52	Fiji
52	Saudi Arabia
51	Malta
51	Mauritius
50	Croatia
50	Malaysia
49	Greece
49	Namibia
48	Vanuatu
47	Armenia
46	Jordan
46	Kuwait
46	Montenegro
46	Romania
45	Bulgaria
45	Sao Tome and Principe
44	Jamaica
43	Benin
43	Ghana
43	Oman
43	Senegal
43	Solomon Islands
43	Timor-Leste
42	Bahrain
42	China
42	Cuba
42	Hungary

42	Moldova
42	North Macedonia
42	Trinidad and Tobago
41	Burkina Faso
41	Kosovo
41	South Africa
41	Vietnam
40	Colombia
40	Côte d'Ivoire
40	Guyana
40	Suriname
40	Tanzania
40	Tunisia
39	India
39	Kazakhstan
39	Lesotho
39	Maldives
38	Morocco
37	Argentina
37	Albania
37	Belarus
37	Ethiopia
37	Gambia
37	Zambia
36	Algeria
36	Brazil
36	Serbia

36	Ukraine
35	Bosnia and Herzegovina
35	Dominican Republic
35	Egypt
35	Nepal
35	Panama
35	Sierra Leone
35	Thailand
34	Ecuador
34	Indonesia
34	Malawi
34	Philippines
34	Sri Lanka
34	Turkey
33	Angola
33	Mongolia
33	Peru
33	Uzbekistan
32	Niger
31	El Salvador
31	Kenya
31	Mexico
31	Togo
30	Djibouti
30	Eswatini
30	Mauritania

29	Bolivia
29	Pakistan
29	Papua New Guinea
28	Gabon
28	Laos
28	Mali
28	Paraguay
27	Cameroon
26	Guinea
26	Kyrgyzstan
26	Russia
26	Uganda
26	Tanzania
26	Russia
26	Uganda
25	Liberia
25	Madagascar
25	Mozambique
25	Nigeria
24	Bangladesh
24	Central African Republic
24	Iran
24	Lebanon
24	Zimbabwe
23	Azerbaijan
23	Guatemala
23	Honduras
23	Iraq
22	Cambodia

22	Congo
22	Guinea-Bissau
21	Eritrea
20	Afghanistan
20	Burundi
20	Chad
20	Comoros
20	Democratic Republic of the Congo
20	Myanmar
20	Sudan
20	Tajikistan
18	Libya
18	Turkmenistan
17	Equatorial Guinea
17	Haiti
17	Korea, North
17	Nicaragua
16	Yemen
13	South Sudan
13	Syria
13	Venezuela
11	Somalia

*The designers employed and the presentation of material on this map follow the UN practice to the best of our knowledge and as of January 2024. They do not imply the endorsement of any nation on the part of Transparency International concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries.

Proposed Law #4

A law requiring the written publication of the preliminary investigation conducted by ombudsman lawyer to determine whether a case should be dismissed or pursued further

According to Ombudsman Samuel Martires (2024), “To speed up the investigation of complaints, we are trying to merge now the fact-finding office and the preliminary investigation office. So when the complaint is filed, it will be **immediately assigned to a lawyer** who will conduct a case evaluation, and the lawyer will determine whether to proceed with the preliminary investigation or to recommend for the dismissal of the case or to recommend for a case build up”.

The written publication is important to determine whether the assigned lawyer in the Office of the Ombudsman carefully considers all aspects of the case. Some cases can involve billions of government funds, so I think this preliminary investigation should be taken seriously.

The required format and guidelines for making a written publication report shall be standardized with the following:

- a) An executive summary of one to two pages that can easily be understood by the public;
- b) All the facts considered in the case;
- c) All the public officials involved in the case;
- d) The anomalous amount involved; and
- e) The reasons why it should be dismissed or why it should be pursued further.

The above list can be improved in the future after a thorough understanding of the preliminary investigation process. The written publication must be notarized by the assigned lawyer and shall be publicized on the website of the Office of the Ombudsman. I think that important decisions like this should be open, public, and transparent. The reputation of the assigned Ombudsman lawyer is at stake should he/she make any decisions not in favor of the citizens.

Voting system of all ombudsman lawyers, whether they concur or not to the decision one of their member. *Like the concept of supreme court decisions.*

We can also reduce any under-the-table negotiations to dismiss a multi-million or billion case involving government funds. For example, a city with a 4-billion anomaly loan. Any Ombudsman lawyer can easily be tempted with a multi-million retirement fund to influence his decision in dismissing the 4-billion anomaly case.

In the future, we can also analyze the performance of all Ombudsman lawyers who handle graft and corruption cases. Every year, we can remove the bottom 20% of underperforming lawyers and replace them with new and capable lawyers who can courageously fight corruption by all legal means.

Other alternatives to the removal of the bottom 20% of underperforming Ombudsman lawyers include:

- Forcing early retirement with basic pension retirement funds.
- Forcing early retirement with a pension salary equal to the average monthly salary of their years in service.

With this strategy, we can improve our perceived corruption index in **Transparency International**. This can encourage foreign investors and improve the quality of life for many Filipinos, as corruption is the root cause of poverty.

Proposed Law #4

A law forbidding politicians to pay debt of gratitude to anyone after election

Example: Elon Musk helped Donald Trump in the 2024 election campaign and then ended up receiving a government position after the election. This is a common practice among many politicians or anyone running for an elective position.

In the Philippines, a solid supporter of a political candidate can become a department head, government employee, or consultant. Big contracts can also be awarded to businessmen after an election by corrupt public officials.

Paying a debt of gratitude is a common culture or practice among many Filipinos. I think it's the primary source of corruption and can also make the election quite unfair to aspiring politicians who don't have good networks or connections.

Penalty: The penalty is different to every case. For Filipinos who are promoted to high position despite not having any civil service qualification, the appointing politician must return the total salaries earned of that promoted and unqualified Filipino. The Filipino who receives an appointment despite not having a civil service eligibility, will be banned to hold public office for the next three (3) years.

For business related debt of gratitude, the total contract involve must be returned by the Politician to the Republic of the Philippines. One month salary of any public official involve can also be a penalty. If the total contract involve is more than P500,000, perpetual disqualification to public officials involve. All signatories in a business contract because of the payment of debt of gratitude shall also be banned to hold public office for the next three (3) years.

Proposed Law #5

A law converting all real estate properties acquired by public officials
in other countries into a Filipino rest house

Applicable only from 2025 onwards, or in a specific year that will be set forth by the law.

This kind of law will not be passed in the next three years. But I think it's a good law to be passed in the future, maybe three to five years from now. We cannot require all past properties purchased in previous years, as it might cause chaos. And besides, it's impossible to pass this kind of law with the kind of legislators who cannot even pass a simple Freedom of Information Bill.

This can become an ordinance (local law) anytime after a good local politician reads this page, banning local politicians such as mayors or councilors from acquiring real estate properties abroad.

I really don't understand why some politicians and public officials steal money from the government, as if it's a very systemized process of a few million per day. I have an assumption that they invest their money in luxurious real estate abroad.

They should invest in the people, in public schools, and in public hospitals, not in earthly possessions. They must practice and realize what it means to become a real public servant.

FOOD SECURITY

Image by "The Harvesters" by Pieter Bruegel the Elder (1565)

Proposed Law #1

Automatic allocation of funds to farmers devastated by typhoons

Source of funds: Local government funds or the 5% risk disaster fund

Limit to reduce abuse: Maximum of P10,000 per farmer

Automatic allocations can vary based on the following:

- a. Total crops devastated by typhoons
- b. Number of family members
- c. Stages of the crops (near-harvest stage have a different allocation from seed planting)

Proposed Law #2

Institutionalizing the rent of agricultural lands by the local government

Minimum of six (6) months or three (3) years depending on the total hectares of agricultural lands in a City or Municipality.

There are many idle lands in the Philippines. Those lands can be rented by the local government for at least six (6) months. The local government can purchase all the agricultural tools and equipment that farmers can use free of charge.

Amendment to Existing Law

Amend the Tree Planting Legacy of Graduates Act of 2024

At least 50% of the trees to be planted must be fruit bearing tree.

A separate local ordinance can be passed so that all the vacant spaces in the national road shall have fruit bearing trees.

Proposed Law #3

A law requiring cities or municipalities with huge agricultural lands to have
a modern agricultural tools and equipments

Source of funds: National budget or local funds

The tools and equipment can be rented for free by farmers from the LGU.

The goal is to speed up the farming process, including planting, watering, weeding, harvesting, etc.

Proposed Law #4

A law procuring high quality seeds in bulk from other countries

Source of funds: National budget or local funds

Distribute systematically to all farmers across the Philippines.

Bulk buying for huge discounts. Sell at a base price to farmers.

Proposed Law #5

Institutionalizing a website for all the farmers

Track supply and demand in different provinces and cities

Educate farmers about the best practices to have high yields

List banks that can offer loans to farmers at a cheaper interest rate

WAR ON DRUGS

Image Source: © 2017 Erik De Castro / Reuters

Core Principles

Drug addiction should not be considered a crime but a mental health problem. If it is considered a mental health problem, we need to hire many mental health professionals in proportion to the estimated number of drug addicts in a specific city.

The City Mayor can coordinate with the Provincial Governor to determine and adjust the right number of health professionals, as it requires a local budget. The local budget requires a local appropriation ordinance.

Core Principles

There must be a database of suspected drug addicts, and they can undergo a free drug test. If any uniformed official or mental health professional visits the house of a suspected drug addict, the drug test result can be presented.

- The free drug test should be conducted by a highly competent medical professional in a DOH-accredited hospital or clinic.
- The free drug test result should have a QR code for an easy verification process.

Core Principles

Do not kill a suspected drug addict. “Shoot to disarm, not shoot to kill,” according to Former President Fidel Ramos.

In case there is a drug addict with firearms or a drug addict guarded by many people with firearms, and the government wants to rehabilitate that person, there must be a carefully crafted plan of action.

Plan of Action (War on Drugs)

- Police officers should have body cams recording the whole process.
- The police officer should not be the first to fire but should only fire once the drug addict fires their gun first.

Plan of Action (War on Drugs)

- Police officers should have 100% bullet protection to reduce the chance of getting killed.
- Only shoot in non-crucial body parts such as the arm, buttocks, or legs, as suggested by Former President Ramos.
- Only arrest a drug addict, not a suspected drug addict. There must be a written, verified testimony from someone stating that the specific person to be arrested is a drug addict.
- If it is later proven through a drug test that the “arrested drug addict” is not actually a drug addict, the person who reported them shall be charged P1,000.
- If it is later proven that the person arrested is indeed a drug addict, the person who reported them shall be rewarded P1,000.

Plan of Action (War on Drugs)

- This is one way to utilize intelligence funds properly - offering small incentives, not huge amounts of government funds.

Arresting a suspect is unconstitutional as it goes against due process, so there must be an enabling law to implement the war on drugs. And if there is an enabling law, it can be questioned up to the Supreme Court.

This is just a hypothetical plan of action against the war on drugs, in case we implement it in the future after having an enabling law.

Proposed Law #1

A law institutionalizing drug addiction rehabilitation and education

Bill of Rights – 1987 Philippine Constitution

Section 1: No person shall be deprived of life, liberty, or property without due process of law, nor shall any person be denied the equal protection of the laws.

WAR

The Third of May by Francisco Goya (2012)

WAR

The Terror of War by Nick Ut, Associated Press (1972)

“It is easier to start a war than to end it.” – Gabriel Garcia Marquez

We need to be specific in handling war, as sometimes it can spiral out of control.

War can cost more than a hundred important human lives, both military and civilian.

Proposed Law #1

A law institutionalizing the negotiation process to prevent and end war

Woodrow Wilson Fourteen Points in 1918. First point:

I. Open covenants of peace, openly arrived at, after which there shall be no private international understandings of any kind but diplomacy shall proceed always frankly and in the public view.

Important Provisions:

1. Continuous negotiations, five days a week, 8 hours per day, until a final resolution is reached that is agreeable to both parties;
2. The negotiations should be open and transparent, with all parties seated at one negotiation table, and the number of arbiters or moderators equal to the number of parties. The proceedings should be recorded, televised, and open to the media. There is no need for a public audience in the negotiation room, as the presence of an audience may create noise that could affect or influence the participants' thinking. Only heads of state and moderators/arbiters should be present

Important Provisions:

The lives of many people are at stake during wars; the public must know whether “what each leader is fighting for is worth fighting for”.

The eight hours shall be broken down as follows:

a. **First 30 minutes:** Both parties shall have a clearly written document stating their demands, objectives, non-negotiables, and contingency plans. They will submit it simultaneously to the arbiters/moderators to be read aloud. They can also attach supporting documents in Annex, stating the basis of their demands, objectives, and non-negotiables.

Important Provisions:

b. **First three hours:** To be moderated by the arbiter from Country 1. Each party will explain the basis of their demands, objectives, etc., so the public can determine whether they are logical, reasonable, and well-founded, and so that the other party can clearly understand their position.

c. Break of 1 hour

d. **Second three hours:** To be moderated by arbiter of country 2. This is to ensure better representation of each country.

e. **Last 30 minutes:** Arbiters / moderators shall provide a summary and recommendations on how to achieve a peaceful resolution.

Important Provisions:

f. The negotiations shall continue the next day and can be non-stop until a final resolution is reached. Breaks can be taken twice a week, such as on Saturday and Sunday, for each party to refresh, hold consultations, and gain a better perspective.

g. The negotiation shall be between heads of state. The Philippines can be represented by the President, Senate President, or the Secretary of Foreign Affairs.

For other forms of government, other countries on the opposite side of the table can be represented by their Prime Minister, Minister, or any of their chosen representatives. *Ideally, with at least 3 years of negotiation experience.*

Again, the lives of many people are at stake during the war. A peaceful resolution should be negotiated by the head of state. The first default negotiator shall be the President of the Philippines, unless otherwise specified by the law.

This process is applicable to the ongoing wars in other countries, such as Ukraine-Russia war, and Israel-Palestine war. If their head of state could have just negotiated continuously in an open and transparent manner until there is a peaceful resolution, they could have saved thousands of lives.

“It can be stressful for the leaders of the state to engage in continuous negotiations, working full-time eight hours per day. It’s better negotiate peacefully than wasting important human lives.” – Jp

Variations:

1. Instead of arbiters – use judge with at least five years experience and must be a lawyer. This is to ensure that what is being discussed or negotiated is within the bounds of the law of each country. Two judges to represent two countries.
2. John Becrow as moderator and use Robert's Rule of Order to facilitate debate.
3. The moderator or speaker can be negotiated.

John Becrow – **10 years** as moderator or speaker of a parliament with **650 Members**.

Image Source: robertsrules.com

The image on the right shows the importance of having a proposed law to avoid war.

They are not just a mere figure, but they represent fathers, mothers, families, children, and thousands of innocent lives.

Image Source:

Al Jazeera, Palestinian Ministry of Health, Palestinian Red Crescent Society, Israeli Army, Israel's Social Security Agency
Data from October 7, 2023 to February 3, 2025

THE TEXT OF THE FOURTEEN POINTS

PRESIDENT WILSON'S *Fourteen Points*, as set forth in an address made before the joint session of Congress, on January 8, 1918.

- 1** Open covenants of peace openly arrived at, after which there shall be no private international understandings of any kind, but diplomacy shall proceed always frankly and in the public view.
- 2** Absolute freedom of navigation upon the seas outside territorial waters alike in peace and in war, except as the seas may be closed in whole or in part by international action or the enforcement of international covenants.
- 3** The removal, so far as possible, of all economic barriers and the establishment of an equality of trade conditions among all the nations consenting to the peace and associating themselves for its maintenance.
- 4** Adequate guarantees given and taken that national armaments will be reduced to the lowest point consistent with domestic safety.
- 5** A free, open-minded and absolutely impartial adjustment of all colonial claims based upon a strict observance of the principle that in determining all such questions of sovereignty the interests of the populations concerned must have equal weight with the equitable claims of the government whose title is to be determined.
- 6** The evacuation of all Russian territory, and such a settlement of all questions affecting Russia as will secure the best and freest cooperation of the other nations of the world in obtaining for her an unhampered and unembarrassed opportunity for the independent determination of her own political development and national policy, and assure her of a sincere welcome into the society of free nations under institutions of her own choosing; and, more than a welcome, assistance also of every kind that she may need and may herself desire. The treatment accorded Russia by her sister nations in the months to come will be the acid test of their goodwill, of their comprehension of her needs as distinguished from their own interests, and of their intelligent and unselfish sympathy.
- 7** Belgium, the whole world will agree must be evacuated and restored, without any attempt to limit the sovereignty which she enjoys in common with all other free nations. No other single act will serve as this will serve to restore confidence among the nations in the laws which they have themselves set and determined for the government of their relations with one another. Without this healing act the whole structure and validity of international law is forever impaired.
- 8** All French territory should be freed and the invaded portions restored, and the wrong done to France by Prussia in 1871 in the matter of Alsace-Lorraine, which has unsettled the peace of the world for nearly fifty years, should be righted, in order that peace may once more be made secure in the interest of all.
- 9** A readjustment of the frontiers of Italy should be effected along clearly recognizable lines of nationality.
- 10** The peoples of Austria-Hungary, whose place among the nations we wish to see safeguarded and assured, should be accorded the freest opportunity of autonomous development.
- 11** Rumania, Serbia and Montenegro should be evacuated; occupied territories restored; Serbia accorded free and secure access to the sea; and the relations of the several Balkan States to one another determined by friendly counsel along historically established lines of allegiance and nationality; and international guarantees of the political and economic independence and territorial integrity of the several Balkan States should be entered upon.
- 12** The Turkish portions of the present Ottoman Empire should be assured a secure sovereignty, but the other nationalities which are now under Turkish rule should be assured an undoubted security of life and an absolutely unmolested opportunity of autonomous development, and the Dardanelles should be permanently opened as a free passage to the ships and commerce of all nations under international guarantees.
- 13** An independent Polish State should be erected which should include the territories inhabited by indisputably Polish populations, which should be assured a free and secure access to the sea, and whose political and economic independence and territorial integrity should be guaranteed by international covenant.
- 14** A general association of nations must be formed under specific covenants for the purpose of affording mutual guarantees of political independence and territorial integrity to great and small States alike.

South China Sea

Woodrow Wilson Fourteen Points in 1918. Second point:

II. Absolute freedom of navigation upon the seas outside territorial waters alike in peace and in war, except as the seas may be closed in whole or in part by international action or the enforcement of international covenants.

Solution: Find a competent arbitrator or moderator, agreeable to both the Philippines and China, then implement Robert's Rules of Order to facilitate debate.

United Arab Emirates

Discovery of oil Abu Dhabi in 1958.

United Arab Emirates production:

- Average Production (2013-2022): **2.9 million barrels per day**
- 2022 Production: **3.07 million barrels per day**

In peso (₱3,776 per barrel):

- $₱3,776 \times 2.9 \text{ million} = \mathbf{₱10.95 \text{ billion per day}}$
- $₱10.95\text{B} \times 365 \approx \mathbf{₱3.997 \text{ trillion/year}}$

Assumption:

The oil in the West Philippine Sea, East Philippine Sea, and Benham Rise can elevate the Philippines to first-world country status within the next 25 years.

Proposal

Joint Venture Agreement with the
top 10 oil and gas companies in the world,
except
China National Offshore Oil Corporation
(CNOOC)

PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION

Image Source: GregReese (2018)

Proposed Law #1

A law institutionalizing point to point system of double deck bus
or any other public utility vehicle in every City.

The Story of PUV in some parts of the Philippines

The goal:

- Reduce traffic
- Reduce drop-out rates of students
- Improve the public transportation of the Filipinos, thus increasing more quality time with their families

The goal:

- Reduce carbon emissions by decreasing the vehicles in the road
- Discourage the use of private vehicles if this point-to-point system in every City becomes efficient. Road accident will also decrease if there are fewer vehicles in the road.

The primary goal is to reduce the travel time from schools and workplaces to home to a maximum of 30 minutes in a city. The funds can be sourced from each city, but if the city doesn't have enough funds, then they can come from the national fund. Traffic can cause stress and a reduced quality of time with the family. It can also be a factor in why students drop out of school.

After visiting many places in the Philippines, I noticed that there are rural areas with no Public Utility Vehicle (PUV). Imagine your experience during the pandemic or during a jeepney strike - that's the life many Filipinos experience every day in those rural areas with no PUV.

Different variations of this law:

A law or ordinance requiring the procurement of double-deck vehicles in proportion to the population of a local government unit. Cities with high populations would end up having more than one double-deck bus in the first year after the passage of this law or ordinance.

Budget Estimate:

- There are more than 149 cities in the Philippines as of July 2023.
- A double-decker bus can cost Php 18 million
- 149 cities x Php 18 million = P2.682 billion

All cities must have at least one double-decker bus in the first year after the passage of this law, and the number should be increased every year until the travel time is reduced to a maximum of 30 minutes in a city.

The double-decker bus can be operated by the city and may be provided for free to poor but deserving students.

MONEY

Filtered by: Money

Gov't allots P2.2 billion to subsidize PUV modernization – LTFRB

Published July 2, 2017 9:47pm

Finance officials have approved an P80,000 subsidy for each of at least 28,000 jeepneys under the public utility vehicle (PUV) modernization program, the Land Transportation and Franchising Regulatory Board (LTFRB) said Sunday.

Image: spaceaero2, 2023 under CC BY-SA 3.0

Image: cdcaustralia, 2022

fact:
**SCHOOL BUSES KEEP
OVER 17 MILLION CARS
OFF ROADS EACH YEAR**

ONE SCHOOL BUS CARRIES THE EQUIVALENT OF **36 CARS**

AMERICAN SCHOOL BUS COUNCIL

AN ANNUAL SAVINGS TO
FAMILIES OF APPROXIMATELY

62 BILLION MILES OF DRIVING
2.6 BILLION GALLONS OF FUEL
56.5 BILLION POUNDS OF CO₂

Proposed Law #2

Public Utility Vehicle (PUV) Modernization

Empathize with the PUV drivers

Old jeepneys can be donated to LGU with no PUV

Gradual implementation of PUV Modernization, then make a study

Image: LMP 2001, 2023

Discounted Price Double Decker Bus Chinese Yutong 6100 Cheap Bus 55 Seats for Sale

US\$15,500.00

1-9 Pieces

US\$13,500.00

10+ Pieces

Product Details >

Customization:	Available
Style:	Sitting
Emission Standard:	Euro 3

[Start Order Request](#)

[Contact Supplier](#)

 [Chat](#)

Shipping & Policy

According to Senator Raffy Tulfo (2024), “Sa pakikipagusap ko sa iba't-ibang miyembro ng transport groups, lumitaw na ang PUV modernization program ay hindi pinag-isipan, hindi pinag-aralan, hindi pinagplanuhan at minadali.”

Senate President Francis Escudero first suggested the suspension of Jeepney Modernization.

WASTE MANAGEMENT

Image Source: zibik (2019)

Image Source: Spittelau incineration plant in Vienna By C.Stadler / Bwag (2020)

Proposed Law #1

A law requiring all LGU with at least P500 million annual budget to have its own
Waste Management Facility and Collection System

Plan of Action:

1. Buy trucks and hire local people for garbage collection.
2. Take a loan for the creation of this Waste Management Facility.
Instead of having an outside contractor that can cost at least P125 million per year, it is financially wise for a City to have its own Waste Management Facility and Collection System.

3. We can have a cost-benefit analysis in the short term and long term of having every Waste Management Facility and Collection System for every City.

4. **Third priority** after FREE education to all college students, and after having an adequate public hospitals.

Assumption:

We can save hundreds of millions in the long term.

Garbage collected by small garbage trucks is dropped in a hopper, compressed in containers and reloaded onto larger trucks. In this transfer station, garbage collected by three 2-ton trucks can be compressed in one container.

The container is then transported to a disposal site or incineration plant on a large container truck.

Source: ShinMaywa Industries, Ltd.

Safety, loading efficiency and operability are required for garbage collection trucks. Smaller trucks have openings set less than 800mm above the ground to realize outstanding workability and operability.

- Low-pollution garbage collection trucks (Example)
Generally, garbage loading and unloading is powered by the engine. This type of truck generates electricity required for loading and unloading while the truck is running. This reduces the consumption of light oil and CO₂ emissions.

Source: ShinMaywa Industries, Ltd.

● Reduced dioxin emissions by 98% compared to 1997 from incineration plants in Japan

Note: ※The value for 2004 and reduction target are expressed in percent to the 2003 value
 Source: Ministry of the Environment

PET bottles at collection

Sorting

PET bottles when delivered to recycling operators

Source: The Council for PET Bottle Recycling

Proposed Law #2

A law adopting the Legal System for
Establishing a “Sound Material-Cycle Society” of Japan

What is Sound Material-Cycle Society of Japan?

“A society in which the consumption of natural resources will be conserved and the environmental load will be reduced to the greatest extent possible, by preventing or reducing the generation of wastes, etc. from products, etc., by promoting proper cyclical use of products, etc. when these products, etc. have become circulative resources, and by ensuring proper disposal of circulative resources not put into cyclical use.” (The Basic Act for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society, 2010).

Legal System for Establishing a "Sound Material-Cycle Society"

The Basic Environment Law

The Basic Law for Environmental Pollution Control in 1967
Enacted in 1993

○Provides basic policies for environmental conservation

Basic Environmental Plan

Established in 1994

(Ministry of the Environment)

The Basic Act for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society (Basic Framework Act)

Enacted 2000

●Provides basic principles related to the establishment of material-cycle society

(To ensure material-cycle society,
control consumption of natural resources,
and reduce environmental load)

○Basic Principle, ○Responsibility of the State, local government, business operators, and citizens, ○Policies of the State

The Fundamental Plan for Establishing a Sound Material-Cycle Society

Enacted 2003

(Ministry of the Environment)

Waste Management and Public Cleansing Law

Enacted in 1970 (Ministry of the Environment)

- ① Appropriate treatment of waste
- ② Rules for establishing waste treatment facility
- ③ Rules for waste treatment businesses
- ④ Waste treatment standards, etc.

Law for the Promotion of Sorted Collection and Recycling Containers and Packaging

Enacted in 1995 (Ministry of the Environment; Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry; and others)

- Collection of containers and packaging by municipalities
- Recycling of containers and packaging by producers and users

Law for the Recycling of Specified Kinds of Home Appliances

Enacted in 1998 (Ministry of the Environment; Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry)

- Retailers receiving used appliances from consumers
- Recycling by manufacturers, etc.
- Consumers shouldering cost for recycling

Construction Material Recycling Law

Enacted in 2000 (Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism; Ministry of the Environment)

- Construction contractors are responsible for the sorting and dismantling
- Construction constructors are responsible for the recycling of construction waste

Law for the Promotion of Effective Utilization of Resources

Enacted in 1991 (Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry; and others)

- Strengthens recycling measures through the collection and recycling of used products by businesses, and stipulates measures to promote the use of recyclable resources through the control of waste generation (reduce), such as by resource saving in manufacturing operations and the manufacture of products with longer lives, and the reuse of parts from collected products (reuse).
- Promote the recycling of home-use computers

Law for promotion of Recycling and Related Activities for treatment of Cyclical Food Resources

Enacted in 2000 (Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries; Ministry of the Environment)

- Recycling of food waste by food manufacturer, processors and sellers

Law for the Recycling of End-of-Life Vehicles

Enacted in 2002 (Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry; Ministry of the Environment; Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism)

- Recycling of end-of-life vehicles
- Payment of recycling fee at the time of purchase of new vehicle

Law concerning the Promotion of Procurement of Eco-Friendly Goods and Services by the State and Other Entities (Law for the Promoting Green Purchasing)

Enacted in 2000 (Ministry of the Environment)

Promotion of procurement of eco-friendly goods and services by the government and other entities

Existing Law:

Republic Act No. 9003 – Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000

Amendment:

- Mandatory Waste Management Facility and Collection System for every LGU that spend more than 100 million per year for waste disposal;
- Minimum wage of P300 per hour. Maximum of 20 hours per week every constituent.
- Maximum of one breadwinner per family. *Improving the quality of life of many Filipino families;*
- Procurement of garbage collector vehicles every barangay;

RENEWABLE ENERGY

Image Source: Solarimo (2020)

Proposed Law #1

A Law Providing for the Rehabilitation, Safe Operation, and Regulation of the
Bataan Nuclear Power Plant, and for Other Purposes

Countries with Nuclear Power Plant:

- United States (**67 years** of operation)
- France (**62 years** of operation)
- Japan (**59 years** of operation)
- South Korea (**47 years** of operation)
- Canada (**63 years** of operation)

U.S. Nuclear Reactors Among the Oldest in the World

Mean age of nuclear reactor fleets in selected countries in 2022* (in years)

Excludes reserve reactors

* as of July 1

Source: World Nuclear Industry Status Report 2022

Image Source: George Buid (2024)

Image Source: Jonah JM (2019)

Facts:

\$6 billion to \$10 billion per reactor or (P336 billion to P560 billion)

Bataan Power Plant is located near a major geographical fault line

4,000 + defects

Important Provisions:

- Hire Japanese to fix the existing 4,000+ defects;
- Initial one reactor in the first three year, then gradually increase over time; Reactor built for earthquake;
- Private Partnership Project to minimize the initial cost.
 - 80-20 split until all initial investment is paid
 - Back to 60-40 split after the initial investment is paid
 - 15 to 30 years usual ROI

Proposed Law #2

A law requiring all government infrastructures to have solar panel

Includes

All public schools (aircon during summer)

- Prioritize schools with cities of more than 40 degree Celsius

All public hospitals

All barangays

OTHER LAWS

Statue of Lady Justice blindfolded and holding a balance and a sword, outside the Court of Final Appeal, Hong Kong. Photographed by ChvhLR10 (2008) under CC BY-SA 3.0

Proposed Law #1

A law prohibiting the firing of a gun into the sky

Insider Tech. (2016, August 1). *Firing a bullet straight up* [Video].
YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qFP3npxIJVk>

Philippine Daily Inquirer. (2024, January 1). *PNP: 1 dead, 1 hurt due to stray bullets on New Year's Eve*. Inquirer.net.
<https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1865665/pnp-1-dead-1-hurt-due-to-stray-bullets-on-new-years-eve>

Penalty and Reward System:

Penalty: P15,000 to the person who fires a gun in the sky.

Perpetual ban to hold a gun.

Reward: P15,000 to any person who will report someone via video of any person who fire a gun into the Sky.

P15,000 can be changed to any value higher than P15,000.

If the person who fires a gun in the sky is a public official, one month salary is the penalty.

One month salary as a penalty can be changed to any penalty higher than one month.

Proposed Law #2

A law increasing the minimum monthly retirement pension
based on the regional minimum wage

The Minimum Monthly Pension can be based on the following:

- a. NCR: Minimum wage per day x 30
 - a. Php 645 per day x 30 = P19,350 per month
- b. Region IV-A: Minimum wage per day x 30
 - a. Php520 per day x 30 = P15,600 per month
- c. Other regions will have a different minimum monthly pension, as their minimum wages are different.

Proposed Law #3

A law prohibiting speed racing in curve roads

Other option to reduce deadly accident: road barrier or divider

Image source: Google Map Streetview near St Louis University in Baguio

Proposed Law #4

A law ADOPTING the Strict Gun Ownership of Japan

According to Kopel (1992):

- Other than the police and the military, no one in Japan may purchase a handgun or a rifle.
- The police check gun licensees' ammunition inventory to make sure there are no shells or pellets unaccounted for.
- A prospective gun owner must take an official safety course and pass a test covering:
 - Maintenance and inspection
 - Loading and unloading
 - Shooting from various positions
 - Target practice for stationary and moving objects
- The license is valid for 3 years.
- When not in use, all guns must be stored in a locked space.

Proposed Law #5

Amendment to the Proposed Divorce Law

Three Equal Consideration

Church

Spouses

Children

Your Vote is Valuable

It can change the future

Your Vote is Valuable (*Three Years Automatic VAT*)

12% Value Added Tax (VAT) in Three Years

Low income but not poor (VAT contribution)

- P47,334 to P94,668

Lower middle class (VAT contribution)

- P94,668 to P189,337

Middle class (VAT contribution)

- P189,337 to P331,210

TWO POLITICAL INVENTIONS:

The Statesman's Affidavit

Fair Debate Framework with Questions from the Citizens

Republic of the Philippines

City of _____

S.S.

SWORN AFFIDAVIT OF DECLARATION

I, _____, of legal age, Filipino, [single/married], and resident of _____, Philippines, after having been duly sworn in accordance with the law, do hereby promised to do the following if elected as Mayor of _____ City:

The first ordinance that I will sign as City Mayor is the ordinance **ADOPTING** the Freedom of Information Ordinance of Pasig City with the title:

“AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.” (Ordinance Number 37; Series of 2018; 12 pages)

By adopting this ordinance, I commit to ensuring its full implementation and enforcement in accordance with its provisions.

I understand that transparency and accountability in governance are vital for the trust and welfare of the people, and I commit to upholding these principles through the enforcement of this ordinance.

In the first year of my term, I shall also prioritize the following ordinances:

- 1. Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance
- 2. Anti-Epal Ordinance
- 3. SALN Publication Ordinance
- 4. Fair Debate Framework Ordinance
- 5. Full-time Politician Ordinance
- 6. _____

As a commitment to my pledge, I **shall resign** as City Mayor if I fail to sign the above ordinances within the first year of my term.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, I have hereunto affixed my signature this ___ day of April, 2025 at _____.

Public Servant

SUBSCRIBED AND SWORN to before me this ___ day of April 2025, at _____ Affiant exhibited to me his/her valid government-issued ID

Republic of the Philippines
SANGGUNIANG PANLUNGSOD
City Government of Pasig

Ordinance No. 37
Series of 2018

AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.

Authored by: Councilor Victor Ma. Regis N. Sotto
Co-Authored by: Councilors Rodrigo B. Asilo, Ferdinand A. Avis, Regino S. Balderrama, Orlando R. Benito, Rhichie Gerard T. Brown, Mario C. Concepcion, Jr., Rosalio D. Martires, Corazon M. Raymundo, Gregorio P. Rupisan, Jr., Alejandro E. Santiago, Wilfredo F. Sityar, LIGA Pres. Rigor J. Enriquez and SK Fed. President Georgia Lynne P. Clemente

First Page of the Freedom of Information Ordinance in
Pasig City Government, 2018, *City Ordinance No. 37, s. 2018*

“AN ORDINANCE STRENGTHENING THE OPERATIONALIZATION OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND PROVIDING FOR A MECHANISM FOR THE DISCLOSURE OF PUBLIC RECORDS IN PASIG CITY, AND PROVIDING PENALTIES FOR THE VIOLATION THEREOF.” (*Ordinance Number 37; Series of 2018; 12 pages*)

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PROMISE + OBLIGATION + PENALTY

TO BE CONTINUED...

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Poor Man's Copyright: *May 2024 up to present*

Since May 2024, every time I come up with a new idea, I've been emailing it to myself as a timestamped record.

Sent to the email addresses of Transparency International, the Open Government Partnership, and the Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance, as some concepts - like **The Statesman's Affidavit** - are highly original, impactful, and capable of transforming a nation.

CERTIFICATION AGAINST INTELLECTUAL FRAUD AND DISHONESTY

I hereby declare, upon my honor, that what I have written in this paper are the products of my own personal intellect and I have made the proper attribution of sources and references. In the event that it is established by the reader that what I have written in this paper had been obtained by me through fraudulent use of ideas or information belonging to other persons, I will acknowledge the findings and will update the citations and reference section of this paper.

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December 9, 2024

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